

Minimum Perfect Square Sum Bordered and Block-Wise Bordered Magic Squares: Orders 3 to 31

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Abstract

*There are many ways of writing magic or **bordered** magic squares, where the sum of entries is always a **perfect square**. In one of the possibility, the magic sums are such that they satisfy **uniformity property**. Another way is to write magic squares generated by **Pythagorean triples**. Based on these idea, we can always write magic squares or **bordered** magic squares where the sum of entries is always a **perfect square**. Still, these sums are not minimum. There is a third way to write magic squares or **bordered** squares such that we get **minimum perfect square sum** of entries. This what we have done in this work with **bordered** and **block-wise bordered** magic squares. In case of even order magic squares, we can always write **block-wise bordered** magic squares with equal sum sub-blocks [25]. In case of odd order magic squares, we can write them as **block-wise bordered** magic squares, but with different sub-blocks sums [24]. This work is for the orders 3 to 31. The extension to **bordered** magic squares of orders 32 to 47 is given in another works. Recently, author [29] applied this idea of **perfect square sum** of entries to write area representations of magic squares.*

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1 Perfect Square Sum of Entries

In this section, we shall write different ways to obtain magic squares in such a way that sums of entries turns to be a **perfect square**. This process is given in following three subsection in different way.

1.1 Uniformity Property

In [27], the author showed that magic square with entries sum a **perfect square** can be constructed in different ways. These are summarized in following results.

Result 1. *A magic square with **perfect square sum** of entries given by*

Magic Square Order:	$k;$
Odd numbers entries:	$M := \{1, 3, 5, \dots, 2k^2 - 3, 2k^2 - 1\};$
Natural numbers entries:	$K := \left\{ \frac{k^2 + 1}{2}, \frac{k^2 + 3}{2}, \dots, \frac{3(k^2 - 1)}{2} - 1, \frac{3k^2 - 1}{2} \right\};$
Magic Square Sum:	$S_{k \times k} := k^3;$
Total Entries Sum:	$T_{k^2} := k^4.$

For simplicity, let’s represent the **uniformity** as,

$$\langle k, k^2, k^3, k^4 \rangle \tag{1}$$

where

$k \rightarrow$ **order of a magic square**;

$k^2 \rightarrow$ **total number of entries**;

$k^3 \rightarrow$ **magic square sum**;

$k^4 \rightarrow$ **sum of all the entries of a magic square.**

It happens with following situations:

- (i) magic squares with **consecutive odd numbers** entries starting from 1.
- (ii) magic squares with **consecutive natural numbers** obtained based on odd numbers entries having the same magic sum.

1.2 Pythagorean Triples

The Result 1 is known as magic square with **uniformity property**. There may be many **Pythagorean triples** satisfying sum of magic squares. But not necessarily, these **Pythagorean triples** generates magic squares of same order. Recently, author studied a result where **Pythagorean triples** generating magic squares and the sum of entries are **perfect squares**. This result is given below.

Result 2. A general formula relating **Pythagorean triples** and magic squares given by

$$F(n, k) := (n(2k + n), 2k(k + n), 2k(k + n) + n^2), k \in \mathbf{N}_+, \quad (2)$$

where n is the order of a magic square and k is the gap between two consecutive term of two consecutive **Pythagorean triples** representing same order magic squares. The right side of the function $F(n, k)$ is written in terms of a **Pythagorean triple**, i.e., (a, b, c) .

The entries of magic squares are given by

$$E_1(n, k) := \{4k(k + n) + 1, 4k(k + n) + 3, \dots, 4k(k + n) + 2n^2 - 3, 4k(k + n) + 2n^2 - 1\};$$

$$E_2(n, k) := \left\{4k(k + n) + \frac{n^2 + 1}{2}, 4k(k + n) + \frac{n^2 + 3}{2}, \dots, 4k(k + n) + \frac{3(n^2 - 1)}{2}, 4k(k + n) + \frac{3n^2 - 1}{2}\right\}.$$

The entries $E_1(n, k)$ are for all order magic squares resulting in **consecutive odd numbers**. The entries $E_2(n, k)$ are only for **odd order magic squares** resulting in **consecutive natural numbers**. In this case, the sum of entries is the same in both the situations. In this case, we don't have **uniformity property** given in (??). For $k = 1$,

the **generated** magic squares are with **minimum perfect square sum** of entries satisfying **Pythagorean triples** property. For details refer [26, 27].

The **minimum value** of sums entries is a **perfect square** in relation to **Pythagorean triples** property, but it may be bigger than the one obtained by applying Result 1. There is another way where we can get **perfect square sum** of entries of a magic square not necessarily satisfying **uniformity property** or **Pythagorean triples** property. This process is given below.

1.3 Minimum Perfect Square Sum of Entries

Let us consider

$$\begin{aligned}
 G(n, k) &= T(n) - T(n - k) \\
 &= (n - k + 1) + (n - k + 3) + \dots + n \\
 &= k \left(n - \frac{k - 1}{2} \right), \quad n \geq k, \\
 &= \frac{k}{2} (2n - k + 1), \quad n \geq k
 \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

where

$$T_n := 1 + 2 + 3 + \dots + n = \frac{n(n + 1)}{2}, \quad n \geq 1 \tag{4}$$

The expression (4) is well known sum of the series of positive natural numbers. It is sometimes known as **Pascal's triangle** property.

Result 3. *Let's consider,*

$$L(n, k) := \left(\sqrt{k}, n - k + 1, n, \frac{G(n, k)^2}{\sqrt{k}}, G(n, k)^2, \sqrt{G(n, k)} \right), \tag{5}$$

where $n = m^2 + \frac{p^2 - 1}{2}$, $k = p^2$ and p is the order of a magic square. The first positive values obtained by considering m , $m \in \mathbf{N}_+$ in expression (5) lead us to a magic square with **minimum perfect square sum** of entries.

For simplicity, let's write $L(a, b, c, d, e, f)$, for the representations given in expression (5), where

- $a \rightarrow$ **Order of magic square;** $a = \sqrt{k};$
 $b \rightarrow$ **First member of a sequence;** $b = n - k + 1;$
 $c \rightarrow$ **Last member of a sequence;** $c = n;$
 $d \rightarrow$ **Sum of magic square;** $d = \frac{G(n, k)^2}{\sqrt{k}};$
 $e \rightarrow$ **Sum of entries;** $e = G(n, k)^2;$
 $f \rightarrow$ **Uniformity property,** $a = f$ or $m = p; \sqrt{k} = \sqrt{G(n, k)}.$

...

(6)

1.4 Examples

In Subsections 1.1, 1.2 and 1.3 there are three Results 1, 2 and 3. These results lead us to five different ways of writing magic squares where the sum of entries is always a **perfect square sum**.

Let's consider a **bordered** magic square of orders 8 and 9 with entries, $\{1, 2, \dots, 63\}$ and $\{1, 2, \dots, 81\}$

58	63	3	1	14	52	12	57
55	45	21	48	15	47	19	10
56	42	38	25	28	39	23	9
61	24	31	36	33	30	41	4
11	22	35	32	29	34	43	54
6	16	26	37	40	27	49	59
5	46	44	17	50	18	20	60
8	2	62	64	51	13	53	7

72	2	4	6	7	70	68	66	74
67	58	18	20	21	56	54	60	15
69	55	50	46	31	30	48	27	13
71	57	35	38	43	42	47	25	11
73	59	33	45	41	37	49	23	9
5	19	53	40	39	44	29	63	77
3	17	34	36	51	52	32	65	79
1	22	64	62	61	26	28	24	81
8	80	78	76	75	12	14	16	10

The magic and total entries sums are given by

$$S_{8 \times 8} := 260; \quad T_{64} := 8 \times 260 = 2080;$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} := 195; \quad T_{36} := 6 \times 195 = 1170;$$

$$S_{4 \times 4} := 130; \quad T_{16} := 4 \times 130 = 520;$$

$$T_4 := 130.$$

$$S_{9 \times 9} := 369; \quad T_{81} := 9 \times 369 = 3321;$$

$$S_{7 \times 7} := 287; \quad T_{49} := 7 \times 287 = 2009;$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} := 205; \quad T_{25} := 5 \times 205 = 1435;$$

$$S_{3 \times 3} := 123; \quad T_9 := 3 \times 123 = 369;$$

$$T_1 := 41.$$

From above two examples we observe that the sum of all entries in each is not a perfect squares. The following examples lead us to total sum of entries is always a perfect square but in different situations.

(i) Below are **bordered** magic square of orders 8 with entries, $\{1, 3, \dots, 125, 127\}$ and $\{65/2, 67/2, \dots, 189/2, 191/2\}$ satisfying **uniformity property** given in (1)

115	125	5	1	27	103	23	113
109	89	41	95	29	93	37	19
111	83	75	49	55	77	45	17
121	47	61	71	65	59	81	7
21	43	69	63	57	67	85	107
11	31	51	73	79	53	97	117
9	91	87	33	99	35	39	119
15	3	123	127	101	25	105	13

89,5	94,5	34,5	32,5	45,5	83,5	43,5	88,5
86,5	76,5	52,5	79,5	46,5	78,5	50,5	41,5
87,5	73,5	69,5	56,5	59,5	70,5	54,5	40,5
92,5	55,5	62,5	67,5	64,5	61,5	72,5	35,5
42,5	53,5	66,5	63,5	60,5	65,5	74,5	85,5
37,5	47,5	57,5	68,5	71,5	58,5	80,5	90,5
36,5	77,5	75,5	48,5	81,5	49,5	51,5	91,5
39,5	33,5	93,5	95,5	82,5	44,5	84,5	38,5

In both the examples, the magic and total sum entries are the same. See below:

$$\begin{aligned}
 S_{8 \times 8} &:= 512 = 8^3; & T_{64} &:= 8 \times 512 = 4096 = 64^2 = 8^4; \\
 S_{6 \times 6} &:= 384; & T_{36} &:= 6 \times 384 = 2304 = 48^2; \\
 S_{4 \times 4} &:= 256; & T_{16} &:= 4 \times 256 = 1024 = 32^2; \\
 & & T_4 &:= 256 := 16^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

Both the examples satisfy the **uniformity property** given in (1), i.e., $\langle 8, 8^2, 8^3, 8^4 \rangle$.

(ii) Below are **bordered** magic square of orders 9 with entries, $\{1, 3, \dots, 159, 161\}$ and $\{41, 42, \dots, 119, 121\}$ satisfying **uniformity property** given in (1)

143	3	7	11	13	139	135	131	147
133	115	35	39	41	111	107	119	29
137	109	99	91	61	59	95	53	25
141	113	69	75	85	83	93	49	21
145	117	65	89	81	73	97	45	17
9	37	105	79	77	87	57	125	153
5	33	67	71	101	103	63	129	157
1	43	127	123	121	51	55	47	161
15	159	155	151	149	23	27	31	19

112	42	44	46	47	110	108	106	114
107	98	58	60	61	96	94	100	55
109	95	90	86	71	70	88	67	53
111	97	75	78	83	82	87	65	51
113	99	73	85	81	77	89	63	49
45	59	93	80	79	84	69	103	117
43	57	74	76	91	92	72	105	119
41	62	104	102	101	66	68	64	121
48	120	118	116	115	52	54	56	50

In both the examples, the magic and total sum of entries are the same. See below:

$$\begin{aligned}
 S_{9 \times 9} &:= 729 = 9^3; & T_{81} &:= 9 \times 729 = 6561 = 81^2 = 9^4; \\
 S_{7 \times 7} &:= 567; & T_{49} &:= 7 \times 567 = 3969 = 63^2; \\
 S_{5 \times 5} &:= 405; & T_{25} &:= 5 \times 405 = 2025 = 45^2; \\
 S_{3 \times 3} &:= 243; & T_9 &:= 3 \times 243 = 729 = 27^2; \\
 & & T_1 &:= 81 = 9^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

Both the examples satisfy the **uniformity property** given in (1), i.e., $\langle 9, 9^2, 9^3, 9^4 \rangle$.

(iii) Below are **bordered** magic square of orders 8 with entries, $\{37, 39, \dots, 161, 163\}$ and $\{137/2, 139/2, \dots, 261/2, 263/2\}$ generated by **Pythagorean triple (18, 80, 82)** with least sum of entries:

151	161	41	37	63	139	59	149
145	125	77	131	65	129	73	55
147	119	111	85	91	113	81	53
157	83	97	107	101	95	117	43
57	79	105	99	93	103	121	143
47	67	87	109	115	89	133	153
45	127	123	69	135	71	75	155
51	39	159	163	137	61	141	49

125,5	130,5	70,5	68,5	81,5	119,5	79,5	124,5
122,5	112,5	88,5	115,5	82,5	114,5	86,5	77,5
123,5	109,5	105,5	92,5	95,5	106,5	90,5	76,5
128,5	91,5	98,5	103,5	100,5	97,5	108,5	71,5
78,5	89,5	102,5	99,5	96,5	101,5	110,5	121,5
73,5	83,5	93,5	104,5	107,5	94,5	116,5	126,5
72,5	113,5	111,5	84,5	117,5	85,5	87,5	127,5
75,5	69,5	129,5	131,5	118,5	80,5	120,5	74,5

In both the examples, the magic and total sum entries are the same. See below:

$$\begin{aligned} S_{8 \times 8} &:= 800; & T_{64} &:= 8 \times 800 = 6400 = 80^2; \\ S_{6 \times 6} &:= 600; & T_{36} &:= 6 \times 600 = 3600 = 60^2; \\ S_{4 \times 4} &:= 400; & T_{16} &:= 4 \times 400 = 1600 = 40^2; \\ & & T_4 &:= 1600 := 40^2. \end{aligned}$$

(iv) Below are **bordered** magic square of orders 9 with entries, $\{41, 43, \dots, 199, 201\}$ and $\{81, 82, \dots, 160, 161\}$ generated by **Pythagorean triple (20, 99, 101)** with least sum of entries:

183	43	47	51	53	179	175	171	187
173	155	75	79	81	151	147	159	69
177	149	139	131	101	99	135	93	65
181	153	109	115	125	123	133	89	61
185	157	105	129	121	113	137	85	57
49	77	145	119	117	127	97	165	193
45	73	107	111	141	143	103	169	197
41	83	167	163	161	91	95	87	201
55	199	195	191	189	63	67	71	59

152	82	84	86	87	150	148	146	154
147	138	98	100	101	136	134	140	95
149	135	130	126	111	110	128	107	93
151	137	115	118	123	122	127	105	91
153	139	113	125	121	117	129	103	89
85	99	133	120	119	124	109	143	157
83	97	114	116	131	132	112	145	159
81	102	144	142	141	106	108	104	161
88	160	158	156	155	92	94	96	90

In both the examples, the magic and total sum of entries are the same. See below:

$$\begin{aligned} S_{9 \times 9} &:= 1089 = 9^3; & T_{81} &:= 9 \times 1089 = 9801 = 99^2; \\ S_{7 \times 7} &:= 847; & T_{49} &:= 7 \times 847 = 5929 = 77^2; \\ S_{5 \times 5} &:= 605; & T_{25} &:= 5 \times 605 = 3025 = 55^2; \\ S_{3 \times 3} &:= 363; & T_9 &:= 3 \times 363 = 1089 = 33^2; \\ & & T_1 &:= 121 = 11^2. \end{aligned}$$

(v) Let's consider a **bordered** magic square of orders 8 and 9 with entries, $\{9/2, 11/2, \dots, 133/2, 135/2\}$ and $\{9, 10, \dots, 88, 89\}$ with **minimum perfect square sum** of entries:

61,5	66,5	6,5	4,5	17,5	55,5	15,5	60,5
58,5	48,5	24,5	51,5	18,5	50,5	22,5	13,5
59,5	45,5	41,5	28,5	31,5	42,5	26,5	12,5
64,5	27,5	34,5	39,5	36,5	33,5	44,5	7,5
14,5	25,5	38,5	35,5	32,5	37,5	46,5	57,5
9,5	19,5	29,5	40,5	43,5	30,5	52,5	62,5
8,5	49,5	47,5	20,5	53,5	21,5	23,5	63,5
11,5	5,5	65,5	67,5	54,5	16,5	56,5	10,5

80	10	12	14	15	78	76	74	82
75	66	26	28	29	64	62	68	23
77	63	58	54	39	38	56	35	21
79	65	43	46	51	50	55	33	19
81	67	41	53	49	45	57	31	17
13	27	61	48	47	52	37	71	85
11	25	42	44	59	60	40	73	87
9	30	72	70	69	34	36	32	89
16	88	86	84	83	20	22	24	18

$$\begin{aligned}
 S_{8 \times 8} &:= 288; & T_{64} &:= 8 \times 288 = 2304 = 48^2; \\
 S_{6 \times 6} &:= 216; & T_{36} &:= 6 \times 216 = 1296 = 36^2; \\
 S_{4 \times 4} &:= 144; & T_{16} &:= 4 \times 144 = 576 = 24^2; \\
 & & T_4 &:= 144 = 12^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 S_{9 \times 9} &:= 441; & T_{81} &:= 9 \times 441 = 3969 = 63^2; \\
 S_{7 \times 7} &:= 343; & T_{49} &:= 7 \times 343 = 2401 = 49^2; \\
 S_{5 \times 5} &:= 245; & T_{25} &:= 5 \times 245 = 1225 = 35^2; \\
 S_{3 \times 3} &:= 147; & T_9 &:= 3 \times 147 = 441 = 21^2; \\
 & & T_1 &:= 49 = 7^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

There are five examples for **bordered** magic squares of order 8 and 9 resulting in **perfect square sum** of entries. Out of these five there are only three sums in each case. See below:

$$\begin{aligned}
 S_{8 \times 8} &:= 512 = 8^3; & T_{64} &:= 8 \times 512 = 4096 = 64^2 = 8^4; \\
 S_{8 \times 8} &:= 800; & T_{64} &:= 8 \times 800 = 6400 = 80^2; \\
 S_{8 \times 8} &:= 288; & T_{64} &:= 8 \times 288 = 2304 = 48^2;
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 S_{9 \times 9} &:= 729 = 9^3; & T_{81} &:= 9 \times 729 = 6561 = 81^2 = 9^4; \\
 S_{9 \times 9} &:= 1089 = 9^3; & T_{81} &:= 9 \times 1089 = 9801 = 99^2; \\
 S_{9 \times 9} &:= 441; & T_{81} &:= 9 \times 441 = 3969 = 63^2;
 \end{aligned}$$

The first case is due to **uniformity property**. The second case is due to **Pythagorean triples**. The last one is with **minimum perfect square sum** of entries. The aim of this work is write only the bordered magic squares of orders 3 to 47 resulting in **minimum perfect square sum** of entries. The subsection below give the list of magic square with their respective entries.

1.5 List of Magic Squares

According to formula given in equation (5), below is a list of magic square with entries as **natural numbers** for **odd order magic squares** and **fraction numbers** for **even order magic squares**. Each row brings in sequence as **magic order, magic sum, total sum of entries**. These entries results in **minimum perfect square sum**.

1. Order 3 ,	$S_{3 \times 3} := 12,$	$T_9 := 36 = 6^2,$	$E := \{0, 1, \dots, 7, 8\}$
2. Order 4 ,	$S_{4 \times 4} := 36,$	$T_{16} := 144 = 12^2,$	$E := \{3/2, 5/2, \dots, 31/2, 33/2\}$
3. Order 5 ,	$S_{5 \times 5} := 80,$	$T_{25} := 400 = 20^2,$	$E := \{4, 5, \dots, 27, 28\}$
4. Order 6 ,	$S_{6 \times 6} := 150,$	$T_{36} := 900 = 30^2,$	$E := \{15/2, 17/2, \dots, 83/2, 85/2\}$
5. Order 7 ,	$S_{7 \times 7} := 175,$	$T_{49} := 1225 = 35^2,$	$E := \{1, 2, \dots, 48, 49\}$
6. Order 8 ,	$S_{8 \times 8} := 288,$	$T_{64} := 2304 = 48^2,$	$E := \{9/2, 11/2, \dots, 133/2, 135/2\}$
7. Order 9 ,	$S_{9 \times 9} := 441,$	$T_{81} := 3969 = 63^2,$	$E := \{9, 10, \dots, 88, 89\}$
8. Order 10 ,	$S_{10 \times 10} := 640,$	$T_{100} := 6400 = 80^2,$	$E := \{29/2, 31/2, \dots, 225/2, 227/2\}$
9. Order 11 ,	$S_{11 \times 11} := 704,$	$T_{121} := 7744 = 88^2,$	$E := \{4, 5, \dots, 123, 124\}$
10. Order 12 ,	$S_{12 \times 12} := 972,$	$T_{144} := 11664 = 108^2,$	$E := \{19/2, 21/2, \dots, 303/2, 305/2\}$
11. Order 13 ,	$S_{13 \times 13} := 1300,$	$T_{169} := 16900 = 130^2,$	$E := \{16, 17, \dots, 183, 184\}$
12. Order 14 ,	$S_{14 \times 14} := 1400,$	$T_{196} := 19600 = 140^2,$	$E := \{5/2, 7/2, \dots, 393/2, 395/2\}$
13. Order 15 ,	$S_{15 \times 15} := 1815,$	$T_{225} := 27225 = 165^2,$	$E := \{9, 10, \dots, 232, 233\}$
14. Order 16 ,	$S_{16 \times 16} := 2304,$	$T_{256} := 36864 = 192^2,$	$E := \{33/2, 35/2, \dots, 541/2, 543/2\}$
15. Order 17 ,	$S_{17 \times 17} := 2448,$	$T_{289} := 41616 = 204^2,$	$E := \{0, 1, \dots, 287, 288\}$
16. Order 18 ,	$S_{18 \times 18} := 3042,$	$T_{324} := 54756 = 234^2,$	$E := \{15/2, 17/2, \dots, 659/2, 661/2\}$
17. Order 19 ,	$S_{19 \times 19} := 3724,$	$T_{361} := 70756 = 266^2,$	$E := \{16, 17, \dots, 375, 376\}$
18. Order 20 ,	$S_{20 \times 20} := 4500,$	$T_{400} := 90000 = 300^2,$	$E := \{51/2, 53/2, \dots, 847/2, 849/2\}$
19. Order 21 ,	$S_{21 \times 21} := 4725,$	$T_{441} := 99225 = 315^2,$	$E := \{5, 6, \dots, 444, 445\}$
20. Order 22 ,	$S_{22 \times 22} := 5632,$	$T_{484} := 123904 = 352^2,$	$E := \{29/2, 31/2, \dots, 993/2, 995/2\}$
21. Order 23 ,	$S_{23 \times 23} := 6647,$	$T_{529} := 152881 = 391^2,$	$E := \{25, 26, \dots, 552, 553\}$
22. Order 24 ,	$S_{24 \times 24} := 6936,$	$T_{576} := 166464 = 408^2,$	$E := \{3/2, 5/2, \dots, 1151/2, 1153/2\}$
23. Order 25 ,	$S_{25 \times 25} := 8100,$	$T_{625} := 202500 = 450^2,$	$E := \{12, 13, \dots, 635, 636\}$
24. Order 26 ,	$S_{26 \times 26} := 9386,$	$T_{676} := 244036 = 494^2,$	$E := \{47/2, 49/2, \dots, 1395/2, 1397/2\}$
25. Order 27 ,	$S_{27 \times 27} := 10800,$	$T_{729} := 291600 = 540^2,$	$E := \{36, 37, \dots, 763, 764\}$
26. Order 28 ,	$S_{28 \times 28} := 11200,$	$T_{784} := 313600 = 560^2,$	$E := \{17/2, 19/2, \dots, 1581/2, 1583/2\}$

27. **Order 29**, $S_{29 \times 29} := 12789$, $T_{841} := 370881 = 609^2$, $E := \{21, 22, \dots, 860, 861\}$
28. **Order 30**, $S_{30 \times 30} := 14520$, $T_{900} := 435600 = 660^2$, $E := \{69/2, 71/2, \dots, 1865/2, 1867/2\}$
29. **Order 31**, $S_{31 \times 31} := 15004$, $T_{961} := 465124 = 682^2$, $E := \{4, 5, \dots, 963, 964\}$
30. **Order 32**, $S_{32 \times 32} := 16928$, $T_{1024} := 541696 = 736^2$, $E := \{35/2, 37/2, \dots, 2079/2, 2081/2\}$
31. **Order 33**, $S_{33 \times 33} := 19008$, $T_{1089} := 627264 = 792^2$, $E := \{32, 33, \dots, 1119, 1120\}$
32. **Order 34**, $S_{34 \times 34} := 21250$, $T_{1156} := 722500 = 850^2$, $E := \{95/2, 97/2, \dots, 2403/2, 2405/2\}$
33. **Order 35**, $S_{35 \times 35} := 21875$, $T_{1225} := 765625 = 875^2$, $E := \{13, 14, \dots, 1236, 1237\}$
34. **Order 36**, $S_{36 \times 36} := 24336$, $T_{1296} := 876096 = 936^2$, $E := \{57/2, 59/2, \dots, 2645/2, 2647/2\}$
35. **Order 37**, $S_{37 \times 37} := 26973$, $T_{1369} := 998001 = 999^2$, $E := \{45, 46, \dots, 1412, 1413\}$
36. **Order 38**, $S_{38 \times 38} := 27702$, $T_{1444} := 1052676 = 1026^2$, $E := \{15/2, 17/2, \dots, 2899/2, 2901/2\}$
37. **Order 39**, $S_{39 \times 39} := 30576$, $T_{1521} := 1192464 = 1092^2$, $E := \{24, 25, \dots, 1543, 1544\}$
38. **Order 40**, $S_{40 \times 40} := 33640$, $T_{1600} := 1345600 = 1160^2$, $E := \{83/2, 85/2, \dots, 3279/2, 3281/2\}$
39. **Order 41**, $S_{41 \times 41} := 34481$, $T_{1681} := 1413721 = 1189^2$, $E := \{1, 2, \dots, 1680, 1681\}$
40. **Order 42**, $S_{42 \times 42} := 37800$, $T_{1764} := 1587600 = 1260^2$, $E := \{37/2, 39/2, \dots, 3561/2, 3563/2\}$
41. **Order 43**, $S_{43 \times 43} := 41323$, $T_{1849} := 1776889 = 1333^2$, $E := \{37, 38, \dots, 1884, 1885\}$
42. **Order 44**, $S_{44 \times 44} := 45056$, $T_{1936} := 1982464 = 1408^2$, $E := \{113/2, 115/2, \dots, 3981/2, 3983/2\}$
43. **Order 45**, $S_{45 \times 45} := 46080$, $T_{2025} := 2073600 = 1440^2$, $E := \{12, 13, \dots, 2035, 2036\}$
44. **Order 46**, $S_{46 \times 46} := 50094$, $T_{2116} := 2304324 = 1518^2$, $E := \{63/2, 65/2, \dots, 4291/2, 4293/2\}$
45. **Order 47**, $S_{47 \times 47} := 54332$, $T_{2209} := 2553604 = 1598^2$, $E := \{52, 53, \dots, 2259, 2260\}$

The letter E represents **consecutive natural or fraction numbers** entries; S represents magic square sum and T represents sum of entries resulting in **perfect squares**. The sum of entries results in magic squares always **minimum perfect squares**.

Remark 1.1.(i) In case of **odd order** magic squares, the entries are **consecutive natural numbers**. In case of **even order** magic squares, the entries are **consecutive fraction numbers**.

(ii) Amongst the magic squares studied here the magic squares of orders 7 and 41 are the only ones starting with the number 1 resulting in **minimum perfect square sum** of entries. According to Sloane [2], the next magic square with **consecutive natural numbers** entries starting with the number 1 that yields a **minimum perfect square sum** of entries are of orders, 7, 41, 239, etc.

(iii) The magic square of orders 3 and 17 are the only two among the studied starts from 0 giving **minimum perfect**

square sum of entries. It should be noted that we are only examining **positive entries** for the magic squares.

(iv) We can also obtain **perfect square sum** of entries for negative values, but these situations are not under study.

This section brings **bordered** magic squares of orders 3 to 9 resulting in **minimum perfect square sum** of entries.

2 Magic Square of Order 3 to 9

2.1 Bordered Magic Square of Order 3

Example 1. The **bordered** magic square of order 3 for the **consecutive natural number entries** $\{0, 1, \dots, 7, 8\}$ is given by

1	6	5
8	4	0
3	2	7

Below are details of **magic** and **entries** sums of **bordered** magic square of order 3. The entries sum is **minimum perfect square**:

$$S_{3 \times 3} := 12; \quad T_9 := 3 \times 12 = 36 = 6^2;$$

$$T_1 := 4 = 2^2.$$

2.2 Bordered Magic Square of Order 4

Example 2. The **bordered** magic square of order 4 for the **consecutive fraction entries** $\{3/2, 5/2, \dots, 31/2, 33/2\}$ is given by

14,5	1,5	4,5	15,5
7,5	12,5	9,5	6,5
11,5	8,5	5,5	10,5
2,5	13,5	16,5	3,5

Below are details of **magic** and **entries** sums of **bordered** magic square of order 4. The entries sum is **minimum perfect square**:

$$S_{4 \times 4} := 36; \quad T_{16} := 4 \times 36 = 144 = 12^2;$$
$$T_4 := 36 := 6^2.$$

2.3 Bordered Magic Square of Order 5

Example 3. The **bordered** magic square of order 5 for the **consecutive natural number entries** $\{4, 5, \dots, 27, 28\}$ is given by

25	21	6	5	23
10	13	18	17	22
8	20	16	12	24
28	15	14	19	4
9	11	26	27	7

Below are details of **magic** and **entries** sums of **bordered** magic square of order 5. The entries sum is **minimum perfect square**:

$$S_{5 \times 5} := 80; \quad T_{25} := 5 \times 80 = 400 = 20^2;$$

$$S_{3 \times 3} := 48; \quad T_9 := 3 \times 48 = 144 = 12^2;$$

$$T_1 := 16 = 4^2.$$

2.4 Bordered Magic Square of Order 6

Example 4. The **bordered** magic square of order 6 for the **consecutive fraction entries** $\{15/2, 17/2, \dots, 83/2, 85/2\}$ is given by

37.5	13.5	40.5	7.5	39.5	11.5
34.5	30.5	17.5	20.5	31.5	15.5
16.5	23.5	28.5	25.5	22.5	33.5
14.5	27.5	24.5	21.5	26.5	35.5
8.5	18.5	29.5	32.5	19.5	41.5
38.5	36.5	9.5	42.5	10.5	12.5

Below are details of **magic** and **entries** sums of **bordered** magic square of order 6. The entries sum is **minimum perfect square**:

$$\begin{aligned}
 S_{6 \times 6} &:= 150;7 & T_{36} &:= 6 \times 150 = 900 = 30^2; \\
 S_{4 \times 4} &:= 100; & T_{16} &:= 4 \times 100 = 400 = 20^2; \\
 & & T_4 &:= 100 := 10^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

2.5 Bordered Magic Square of Order 7

Example 5. The **bordered** magic square of order 7 for the **consecutive natural number entries** $\{1, 2, \dots, 48, 49\}$ is given by

42	2	4	5	40	38	44
39	34	30	15	14	32	11
41	19	22	27	26	31	9
43	17	29	25	21	33	7
3	37	24	23	28	13	47
1	18	20	35	36	16	49
6	48	46	45	10	12	8

Below are details of **magic** and **entries** sums of **bordered** magic square of order 7. The entries sum is **minimum perfect square**:

$$S_{7 \times 7} := 175; \quad T_{49} := 7 \times 175 = 1225 = 35^2;$$

$$S_{3 \times 3} := 75; \quad T_9 := 3 \times 75 = 225 = 15^2;$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} := 125; \quad T_{25} := 5 \times 125 = 625 = 25^2;$$

$$T_1 := 25 = 5^2.$$

2.6 Bordered Magic Square of Order 8

Example 6. The **bordered** magic square of order 8 for the **consecutive fraction entries** $\{9/2, 11/2, \dots, 133/2, 135/2\}$ is given by

61.5	66.5	6.5	4.5	17.5	55.5	15.5	60.5
58.5	48.5	24.5	51.5	18.5	50.5	22.5	13.5
59.5	45.5	41.5	28.5	31.5	42.5	26.5	12.5
64.5	27.5	34.5	39.5	36.5	33.5	44.5	7.5
14.5	25.5	38.5	35.5	32.5	37.5	46.5	57.5
9.5	19.5	29.5	40.5	43.5	30.5	52.5	62.5
8.5	49.5	47.5	20.5	53.5	21.5	23.5	63.5
11.5	5.5	65.5	67.5	54.5	16.5	56.5	10.5

Below are details of **magic** and **entries** sums of **bordered** magic square of order 8. The entries sum is **minimum perfect square**:

$$S_{8 \times 8} := 288; \quad T_{64} := 8 \times 288 = 2304 = 48^2;$$

$$S_{4 \times 4} := 144; \quad T_{16} := 4 \times 144 = 576 = 24^2;$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} := 216; \quad T_{36} := 6 \times 216 = 1296 = 36^2;$$

$$T_4 := 144 := 12^2.$$

2.7 Bordered Magic Square of Order 9

Example 7. The **bordered** magic square of order 9 for the **consecutive natural number entries** $\{9, 10, \dots, 88, 89\}$ is given by

80	10	12	14	15	78	76	74	82
75	66	26	28	29	64	62	68	23
77	63	58	54	39	38	56	35	21
79	65	43	46	51	50	55	33	19
81	67	41	53	49	45	57	31	17
13	27	61	48	47	52	37	71	85
11	25	42	44	59	60	40	73	87
9	30	72	70	69	34	36	32	89
16	88	86	84	83	20	22	24	18

Below are details of **magic** and **entries** sums of **bordered** magic square of order 9. The entries sum is **minimum perfect square**:

$$S_{9 \times 9} := 441; \quad T_{81} := 9 \times 441 = 3969 = 63^2;$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} := 245; \quad T_{25} := 5 \times 245 = 1225 = 35^2;$$

$$S_{7 \times 7} := 343; \quad T_{49} := 7 \times 343 = 2401 = 49^2;$$

$$S_{3 \times 3} := 147; \quad T_9 := 3 \times 147 = 441 = 21^2;$$

$$T_1 := 49 = 7^2.$$

3 Magic Squares of Order 10

3.1 Bordered Magic Square of Order 10

This section brings **bordered** and **block-wise bordered** magic squares of orders 10 resulting in **minimum perfect square sum** of entries.

Example 8. The **bordered** magic square of order 10 for the **consecutive fraction entries** $\{29/2, 31/2, \dots, 225/2, 227/2\}$ is given by

104.5	99.5	29.5	97.5	31.5	27.5	17.5	111.5	15.5	105.5
26.5	89.5	94.5	34.5	32.5	45.5	83.5	43.5	88.5	101.5
102.5	86.5	76.5	52.5	79.5	46.5	78.5	50.5	41.5	25.5
24.5	87.5	73.5	69.5	56.5	59.5	70.5	54.5	40.5	103.5
109.5	92.5	55.5	62.5	67.5	64.5	61.5	72.5	35.5	18.5
14.5	42.5	53.5	66.5	63.5	60.5	65.5	74.5	85.5	113.5
106.5	37.5	47.5	57.5	68.5	71.5	58.5	80.5	90.5	21.5
20.5	36.5	77.5	75.5	48.5	81.5	49.5	51.5	91.5	107.5
108.5	39.5	33.5	93.5	95.5	82.5	44.5	84.5	38.5	19.5
22.5	28.5	98.5	30.5	96.5	100.5	110.5	16.5	112.5	23.5

Below are details of **magic** and **entries** sums of **bordered** magic square of order 10. The entries sum is **minimum perfect square**:

$$S_{10 \times 10} := 640; \quad T_{100} := 10 \times 640 = 6400 = 80^2;$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} := 384; \quad T_{36} := 6 \times 384 = 2304 = 48^2;$$

$$S_{8 \times 8} := 512; \quad T_{64} := 8 \times 512 = 4096 = 64^2;$$

$$S_{4 \times 4} := 256; \quad T_{16} := 4 \times 256 = 1024 = 32^2;$$

$$T_4 := 56 := 16^2.$$

3.2 Block-Wise Bordered Magic Squares of Order 10

Example 9. The *block-wise bordered* magic square of order 10 for the *consecutive fraction entries* $\{29/2, 31/2, \dots, 225/2, 227/2\}$ entries is given by

104.5	99.5	29.5	97.5	31.5	27.5	17.5	111.5	15.5	105.5
26.5	60.5	71.5	32.5	91.5	52.5	79.5	40.5	83.5	101.5
102.5	35.5	88.5	63.5	68.5	43.5	80.5	55.5	76.5	25.5
24.5	95.5	36.5	67.5	56.5	87.5	44.5	75.5	48.5	103.5
109.5	64.5	59.5	92.5	39.5	72.5	51.5	84.5	47.5	18.5
14.5	61.5	70.5	33.5	90.5	53.5	78.5	41.5	82.5	113.5
106.5	34.5	89.5	62.5	69.5	42.5	81.5	54.5	77.5	21.5
20.5	94.5	37.5	66.5	57.5	86.5	45.5	74.5	49.5	107.5
108.5	65.5	58.5	93.5	38.5	73.5	50.5	85.5	46.5	19.5
22.5	28.5	98.5	30.5	96.5	100.5	110.5	16.5	112.5	23.5

Below are details of *magic* and *entries* sums of *block-wise bordered* magic square of order 10. The entries sum is *minimum perfect square*. It is formed by inner block of order 8 with equal sums of magic squares of order 4.

$$S_{10 \times 10} := 640; \quad T_{100} := 10 \times 640 = 6400 = 80^2;$$

$$S_{4 \times 4} := 256; \quad T_{16} := 4 \times 256 = 1024 = 32^2;$$

$$S_{8 \times 8} := 512; \quad T_{64} := 8 \times 512 = 4096 = 64^2;$$

$$T_4 := 56 := 16^2.$$

4 Bordered Magic Square of Order 11

This section brings **bordered** magic square of order 11 resulting in **minimum perfect square sum** of entries.

Example 10. The **bordered** magic square of order 11 for the **consecutive natural number entries** $\{4, 5, \dots, 123, 124\}$ is given by

13	4	6	8	10	114	112	110	108	106	113
123	95	25	27	29	30	93	91	89	97	5
121	90	81	41	43	44	79	77	83	38	7
119	92	78	73	69	54	53	71	50	36	9
117	94	80	58	61	66	65	70	48	34	11
116	96	82	56	68	64	60	72	46	32	12
17	28	42	76	63	62	67	52	86	100	111
19	26	40	57	59	74	75	55	88	102	109
21	24	45	87	85	84	49	51	47	104	107
23	31	103	101	99	98	35	37	39	33	105
15	124	122	120	118	14	16	18	20	22	115

Below are details of **magic** and **entries** sums of **bordered** magic square of order 11. The entries sum is **minimum perfect square**:

$$S_{11 \times 11} := 704; \quad T_{121} := 11 \times 704 = 7744 = 88^2;$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} := 320; \quad T_{25} := 5 \times 320 = 1600 = 40^2;$$

$$S_{9 \times 9} := 576; \quad T_{81} := 9 \times 576 = 5184 = 72^2;$$

$$S_{3 \times 3} := 192; \quad T_9 := 3 \times 192 = 576 = 24^2;$$

$$S_{7 \times 7} := 448; \quad T_{49} := 7 \times 448 = 3136 = 56^2;$$

$$T_1 := 64 = 8^2.$$

5 Magic Squares of Order 12

This section brings **bordered** and **block-wise bordered** magic squares of orders 12 resulting in **minimum perfect square sum** of entries.

5.1 Bordered Magic Square of Order 12

Example 11. The **bordered** magic square of order 12 for the **consecutive fraction entries** $\{19/2, 21/2, \dots, 303/2, 305/2\}$ is given by

141.5	137.5	138.5	22.5	21.5	14.5	25.5	143.5	144.5	16.5	146.5	19.5
26.5	121.5	116.5	46.5	114.5	48.5	44.5	34.5	128.5	32.5	122.5	135.5
134.5	43.5	106.5	111.5	51.5	49.5	62.5	100.5	60.5	105.5	118.5	27.5
28.5	119.5	103.5	93.5	69.5	96.5	63.5	95.5	67.5	58.5	42.5	133.5
132.5	41.5	104.5	90.5	86.5	73.5	76.5	87.5	71.5	57.5	120.5	29.5
30.5	126.5	109.5	72.5	79.5	84.5	81.5	78.5	89.5	52.5	35.5	131.5
9.5	31.5	59.5	70.5	83.5	80.5	77.5	82.5	91.5	102.5	130.5	152.5
13.5	123.5	54.5	64.5	74.5	85.5	88.5	75.5	97.5	107.5	38.5	148.5
149.5	37.5	53.5	94.5	92.5	65.5	98.5	66.5	68.5	108.5	124.5	12.5
11.5	125.5	56.5	50.5	110.5	112.5	99.5	61.5	101.5	55.5	36.5	150.5
151.5	39.5	45.5	115.5	47.5	113.5	117.5	127.5	33.5	129.5	40.5	10.5
142.5	24.5	23.5	139.5	140.5	147.5	136.5	18.5	17.5	145.5	15.5	20.5

Below are details of **magic** and **entries** sums of **bordered** magic square of order 12. The entries sum is **minimum perfect square**:

$$S_{12 \times 12} := 972; \quad T_{144} := 12 \times 972 = 11664 := 108^2;$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} := 486; \quad T_{36} := 6 \times 486 = 2916 := 54^2;$$

$$S_{10 \times 10} := 810; \quad T_{100} := 10 \times 810 = 8100 := 90^2;$$

$$S_{4 \times 4} := 324; \quad T_{16} := 4 \times 324 = 1296 := 36^2;$$

$$S_{8 \times 8} := 648; \quad T_{64} := 8 \times 648 = 5184 := 72^2;$$

$$T_4 := 324 := 18^2.$$

5.2 Block-Wise Bordered Magic Square of Order 12

Example 12. The **block-wise bordered** magic square of order 12 for the **consecutive fraction entries** $\{19/2, 21/2, \dots, 303/2, 305/2\}$ is given by

148.5	146.5	11.5	152.5	12.5	14.5	130.5	128.5	29.5	134.5	30.5	32.5
10.5	25.5	138.5	19.5	140.5	151.5	28.5	43.5	120.5	37.5	122.5	133.5
16.5	20.5	139.5	26.5	137.5	145.5	34.5	38.5	121.5	44.5	119.5	127.5
18.5	142.5	21.5	136.5	23.5	143.5	36.5	124.5	39.5	118.5	41.5	125.5
144.5	135.5	24.5	141.5	22.5	17.5	126.5	117.5	42.5	123.5	40.5	35.5
147.5	15.5	150.5	9.5	149.5	13.5	129.5	33.5	132.5	27.5	131.5	31.5
112.5	110.5	47.5	116.5	48.5	50.5	94.5	92.5	65.5	98.5	66.5	68.5
46.5	61.5	102.5	55.5	104.5	115.5	64.5	79.5	84.5	73.5	86.5	97.5
52.5	56.5	103.5	62.5	101.5	109.5	70.5	74.5	85.5	80.5	83.5	91.5
54.5	106.5	57.5	100.5	59.5	107.5	72.5	88.5	75.5	82.5	77.5	89.5
108.5	99.5	60.5	105.5	58.5	53.5	90.5	81.5	78.5	87.5	76.5	71.5
111.5	51.5	114.5	45.5	113.5	49.5	93.5	69.5	96.5	63.5	95.5	67.5

Below are details of **magic** and **entries** sums of **block-wise bordered** magic square of order 12. The entries sum is **minimum perfect square**. It is formed by 4 blocks of **bordered** magic squares of order 6 with equal magic sums.

$$S_{12 \times 12} := 972; \quad T_{144} := 12 \times 972 = 11664 = 108^2;$$

$$S_{4 \times 4} := 324; \quad T_{16} := 4 \times 324 = 1296 = 36^2;$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} := 486; \quad T_{36} := 6 \times 486 = 2916 = 54^2;$$

$$T_4 := 324 := 18^2.$$

6 Bordered Magic Squares of Order 13

This section brings **bordered** magic square of order 13 resulting in **minimum perfect square sum** of entries.

Example 13. The **bordered** magic square of order 13 for the **consecutive natural numbers entries** {16, 17, ..., 183, 184} is given by

27	16	18	20	22	24	172	170	168	166	164	162	171
183	49	40	42	44	46	150	148	146	144	142	149	17
181	159	131	61	63	65	66	129	127	125	133	41	19
179	157	126	117	77	79	80	115	113	119	74	43	21
177	155	128	114	109	105	90	89	107	86	72	45	23
175	153	130	116	94	97	102	101	106	84	70	47	25
174	152	132	118	92	104	100	96	108	82	68	48	26
31	53	64	78	112	99	98	103	88	122	136	147	169
33	55	62	76	93	95	110	111	91	124	138	145	167
35	57	60	81	123	121	120	85	87	83	140	143	165
37	59	67	139	137	135	134	71	73	75	69	141	163
39	51	160	158	156	154	50	52	54	56	58	151	161
29	184	182	180	178	176	28	30	32	34	36	38	173

Below are details of **magic** and **entries** sums of **bordered** magic square of order 13. The entries sum is **minimum perfect square**:

$$S_{13 \times 13} := 1300; \quad T_{169} := 13 \times 1300 = 16900 = 130^2;$$

$$S_{11 \times 11} := 1100; \quad T_{121} := 11 \times 1100 = 12100 = 110^2;$$

$$S_{9 \times 9} := 900; \quad T_{81} := 9 \times 900 = 8100 = 90^2;$$

$$S_{7 \times 7} := 700; \quad T_{49} := 7 \times 700 = 4900 = 70^2;$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} := 500; \quad T_{25} := 5 \times 500 = 2500 = 50^2;$$

$$S_{3 \times 3} := 300; \quad T_9 := 3 \times 300 = 900 = 30^2;$$

$$T_1 := 100 = 10^2.$$

7 Magic Squares of Order 14

This section brings **bordered** and **block-wise bordered** magic squares of orders 14 resulting in **minimum perfect square sum** of entries.

7.1 Bordered Magic Square of Order 14

Example 14. The **bordered** magic square of order 14 for the **consecutive fraction entries** $\{19/2, 21/2, \dots, 303/2, 305/2\}$ is given by

184.5	20.5	180.5	18.5	182.5	16.5	191.5	2.5	186.5	12.5	188.5	10.5	190.5	14.5
177.5	160.5	156.5	157.5	41.5	40.5	33.5	44.5	162.5	163.5	35.5	165.5	38.5	22.5
23.5	45.5	140.5	135.5	65.5	133.5	67.5	63.5	53.5	147.5	51.5	141.5	154.5	176.5
175.5	153.5	62.5	125.5	130.5	70.5	68.5	81.5	119.5	79.5	124.5	137.5	46.5	24.5
25.5	47.5	138.5	122.5	112.5	88.5	115.5	82.5	114.5	86.5	77.5	61.5	152.5	174.5
173.5	151.5	60.5	123.5	109.5	105.5	92.5	95.5	106.5	90.5	76.5	139.5	48.5	26.5
27.5	49.5	145.5	128.5	91.5	98.5	103.5	100.5	97.5	108.5	71.5	54.5	150.5	172.5
21.5	28.5	50.5	78.5	89.5	102.5	99.5	96.5	101.5	110.5	121.5	149.5	171.5	178.5
7.5	32.5	142.5	73.5	83.5	93.5	104.5	107.5	94.5	116.5	126.5	57.5	167.5	192.5
193.5	168.5	56.5	72.5	113.5	111.5	84.5	117.5	85.5	87.5	127.5	143.5	31.5	6.5
5.5	30.5	144.5	75.5	69.5	129.5	131.5	118.5	80.5	120.5	74.5	55.5	169.5	194.5
195.5	170.5	58.5	64.5	134.5	66.5	132.5	136.5	146.5	52.5	148.5	59.5	29.5	4.5
3.5	161.5	43.5	42.5	158.5	159.5	166.5	155.5	37.5	36.5	164.5	34.5	39.5	196.5
185.5	179.5	19.5	181.5	17.5	183.5	8.5	197.5	13.5	187.5	11.5	189.5	9.5	15.5

Below are details of **magic** and **entries** sums of **bordered** magic square of order 14. The entries sum is **minimum perfect square**:

$$S_{14 \times 14} := 1400; \quad T_{196} := 14 \times 1400 = 19600 = 140^2;$$

$$S_{12 \times 12} := 1200; \quad T_{144} := 12 \times 1200 = 14400 = 120^2;$$

$$S_{10 \times 10} := 1000; \quad T_{100} := 10 \times 1000 = 10000 = 100^2;$$

$$S_{8 \times 8} := 800; \quad T_{64} := 8 \times 800 = 6400 = 80^2;$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} := 600; \quad T_{36} := 6 \times 600 = 3600 = 60^2;$$

$$S_{4 \times 4} := 400; \quad T_{16} := 4 \times 400 = 1600 = 40^2;$$

$$T_4 := 400 = 20^2.$$

7.2 Block-Wise Bordered Magic Square of Order 14

Example 15. The **block-wise bordered** magic square of order 14 for the **consecutive fraction entries** $\{5/2, 7/2, \dots, 393/2, 395/2\}$ is given by

15.5	9.5	189.5	11.5	187.5	13.5	197.5	8.5	183.5	17.5	181.5	19.5	179.5	185.5
196.5	167.5	165.5	30.5	171.5	31.5	33.5	149.5	147.5	48.5	153.5	49.5	51.5	3.5
4.5	29.5	44.5	157.5	38.5	159.5	170.5	47.5	62.5	139.5	56.5	141.5	152.5	195.5
194.5	35.5	39.5	158.5	45.5	156.5	164.5	53.5	57.5	140.5	63.5	138.5	146.5	5.5
6.5	37.5	161.5	40.5	155.5	42.5	162.5	55.5	143.5	58.5	137.5	60.5	144.5	193.5
192.5	163.5	154.5	43.5	160.5	41.5	36.5	145.5	136.5	61.5	142.5	59.5	54.5	7.5
178.5	166.5	34.5	169.5	28.5	168.5	32.5	148.5	52.5	151.5	46.5	150.5	50.5	21.5
172.5	131.5	129.5	66.5	135.5	67.5	69.5	113.5	111.5	84.5	117.5	85.5	87.5	27.5
26.5	65.5	80.5	121.5	74.5	123.5	134.5	83.5	98.5	103.5	92.5	105.5	116.5	173.5
174.5	71.5	75.5	122.5	81.5	120.5	128.5	89.5	93.5	104.5	99.5	102.5	110.5	25.5
24.5	73.5	125.5	76.5	119.5	78.5	126.5	91.5	107.5	94.5	101.5	96.5	108.5	175.5
176.5	127.5	118.5	79.5	124.5	77.5	72.5	109.5	100.5	97.5	106.5	95.5	90.5	23.5
22.5	130.5	70.5	133.5	64.5	132.5	68.5	112.5	88.5	115.5	82.5	114.5	86.5	177.5
14.5	190.5	10.5	188.5	12.5	186.5	2.5	191.5	16.5	182.5	18.5	180.5	20.5	184.5

Below are details of **magic** and **entries** sums of **block-wise bordered** magic square of order 14. The entries sum is **minimum perfect square**. It is formed by inner block of magic square of order 12 with 4 blocks of **bordered** magic squares of order 6 with equal magic sums.

$$S_{14 \times 14} := 1400; \quad T_{196} := 14 \times 1400 = 19600 = 140^2;$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} := 600; \quad T_{36} := 6 \times 600 = 3600 = 60^2;$$

$$S_{12 \times 12} := 1200; \quad T_{144} := 12 \times 1200 = 14400 = 120^2;$$

$$S_{4 \times 4} := 400; \quad T_{16} := 4 \times 400 = 1600 = 40^2;$$

$$T_4 := 400 := 20^2.$$

8 Bordered Magic Square of Order 15

This section brings **bordered** magic square of order 15 resulting in **minimum perfect square sum** of entries.

Example 16. *The bordered magic square of order 15 for the consecutive natural number entries {9, 10, ..., 232, 233} is given by*

220	206	208	210	212	214	216	21	20	18	16	14	12	10	218
35	48	37	39	41	43	45	193	191	189	187	185	183	192	207
33	204	70	61	63	65	67	171	169	167	165	163	170	38	209
31	202	180	152	82	84	86	87	150	148	146	154	62	40	211
29	200	178	147	138	98	100	101	136	134	140	95	64	42	213
27	198	176	149	135	130	126	111	110	128	107	93	66	44	215
25	196	174	151	137	115	118	123	122	127	105	91	68	46	217
23	195	173	153	139	113	125	121	117	129	103	89	69	47	219
223	52	74	85	99	133	120	119	124	109	143	157	168	190	19
225	54	76	83	97	114	116	131	132	112	145	159	166	188	17
227	56	78	81	102	144	142	141	106	108	104	161	164	186	15
229	58	80	88	160	158	156	155	92	94	96	90	162	184	13
231	60	72	181	179	177	175	71	73	75	77	79	172	182	11
233	50	205	203	201	199	197	49	51	53	55	57	59	194	9
24	36	34	32	30	28	26	221	222	224	226	228	230	232	22

Below are details of **magic** and **entries** sums of **bordered** magic square of order 15. The entries sum is **minimum perfect square**:

$$S_{15 \times 15} := 1815; \quad T_{225} := 15 \times 1815 = 27225 = 165^2;$$

$$S_{7 \times 7} := 847; \quad T_{49} := 7 \times 847 = 5929 = 77^2;$$

$$S_{13 \times 13} := 1573; \quad T_{169} := 13 \times 1573 = 20449 = 143^2;$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} := 605; \quad T_{25} := 5 \times 605 = 3025 = 55^2;$$

$$S_{11 \times 11} := 1331; \quad T_{121} := 11 \times 1331 = 14641 = 121^2;$$

$$S_{3 \times 3} := 363; \quad T_9 := 3 \times 363 = 1089 = 33^2;$$

$$S_{9 \times 9} := 1089; \quad T_{81} := 9 \times 1089 = 9801 = 99^2;$$

$$T_1 := 121 = 11^2.$$

9 Magic Squares of Order 16

This section brings **bordered** and **block-wise bordered** magic squares of orders 16 resulting in **minimum perfect square sum** of entries.

9.1 Bordered Magic Square of Order 16

Example 17. A *bordered* magic square of order 16 for the *consecutive fraction entries* $\{33/2, 35/2, \dots, 541/2, 543/2\}$ is given by

256.5	250.5	36.5	252.5	253.5	33.5	32.5	23.5	38.5	258.5	259.5	27.5	261.5	25.5	263.5	30.5
39.5	228.5	64.5	224.5	62.5	226.5	60.5	235.5	46.5	230.5	56.5	232.5	54.5	234.5	58.5	248.5
247.5	221.5	204.5	200.5	201.5	85.5	84.5	77.5	88.5	206.5	207.5	79.5	209.5	82.5	66.5	40.5
41.5	67.5	89.5	184.5	179.5	109.5	177.5	111.5	107.5	97.5	191.5	95.5	185.5	198.5	220.5	246.5
245.5	219.5	197.5	106.5	169.5	174.5	114.5	112.5	125.5	163.5	123.5	168.5	181.5	90.5	68.5	42.5
43.5	69.5	91.5	182.5	166.5	156.5	132.5	159.5	126.5	158.5	130.5	121.5	105.5	196.5	218.5	244.5
243.5	217.5	195.5	104.5	167.5	153.5	149.5	136.5	139.5	150.5	134.5	120.5	183.5	92.5	70.5	44.5
45.5	71.5	93.5	189.5	172.5	135.5	142.5	147.5	144.5	141.5	152.5	115.5	98.5	194.5	216.5	242.5
16.5	65.5	72.5	94.5	122.5	133.5	146.5	143.5	140.5	145.5	154.5	165.5	193.5	215.5	222.5	271.5
22.5	51.5	76.5	186.5	117.5	127.5	137.5	148.5	151.5	138.5	160.5	170.5	101.5	211.5	236.5	265.5
266.5	237.5	212.5	100.5	116.5	157.5	155.5	128.5	161.5	129.5	131.5	171.5	187.5	75.5	50.5	21.5
20.5	49.5	74.5	188.5	119.5	113.5	173.5	175.5	162.5	124.5	164.5	118.5	99.5	213.5	238.5	267.5
268.5	239.5	214.5	102.5	108.5	178.5	110.5	176.5	180.5	190.5	96.5	192.5	103.5	73.5	48.5	19.5
18.5	47.5	205.5	87.5	86.5	202.5	203.5	210.5	199.5	81.5	80.5	208.5	78.5	83.5	240.5	269.5
270.5	229.5	223.5	63.5	225.5	61.5	227.5	52.5	241.5	57.5	231.5	55.5	233.5	53.5	59.5	17.5
257.5	37.5	251.5	35.5	34.5	254.5	255.5	264.5	249.5	29.5	28.5	260.5	26.5	262.5	24.5	31.5

Below are details of **magic** and **entries** sums of **bordered** magic square of order 16. The entries sum is **minimum perfect square**:

$$S_{16 \times 16} := 2304; \quad T_{256} := 16 \times 2304 = 36864 = 192^2;$$

$$S_{14 \times 14} := 2016; \quad T_{196} := 14 \times 2016 = 28224 = 168^2;$$

$$S_{12 \times 12} := 1728; \quad T_{144} := 12 \times 1728 = 20736 = 144^2;$$

$$S_{10 \times 10} := 1440; \quad T_{100} := 10 \times 1440 = 14400 = 120^2;$$

$$S_{8 \times 8} := 1152; \quad T_{64} := 8 \times 1152 = 9216 = 96^2;$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} := 864; \quad T_{36} := 6 \times 864 = 5184 = 72^2;$$

$$S_{4 \times 4} := 576; \quad T_{16} := 4 \times 576 = 2304 = 48^2;$$

$$T_4 := 576 := 24^2.$$

9.2 Block-Wise Bordered Magic Square of Order 16

Example 18. The *block-wise bordered* magic square of order 16 for the *consecutive fraction entries* $\{33/2, 35/2, \dots, 541/2, 543/2\}$ is given by

23.5	17.5	269.5	271.5	258.5	28.5	260.5	22.5	55.5	49.5	237.5	239.5	226.5	60.5	228.5	54.5
20.5	253.5	251.5	32.5	257.5	33.5	35.5	267.5	52.5	221.5	219.5	64.5	225.5	65.5	67.5	235.5
21.5	31.5	245.5	40.5	43.5	246.5	256.5	266.5	53.5	63.5	213.5	72.5	75.5	214.5	224.5	234.5
26.5	37.5	46.5	243.5	240.5	45.5	250.5	261.5	58.5	69.5	78.5	211.5	208.5	77.5	218.5	229.5
268.5	39.5	242.5	47.5	44.5	241.5	248.5	19.5	236.5	71.5	210.5	79.5	76.5	209.5	216.5	51.5
263.5	249.5	41.5	244.5	247.5	42.5	38.5	24.5	231.5	217.5	73.5	212.5	215.5	74.5	70.5	56.5
262.5	252.5	36.5	255.5	30.5	254.5	34.5	25.5	230.5	220.5	68.5	223.5	62.5	222.5	66.5	57.5
265.5	270.5	18.5	16.5	29.5	259.5	27.5	264.5	233.5	238.5	50.5	48.5	61.5	227.5	59.5	232.5
87.5	81.5	205.5	207.5	194.5	92.5	196.5	86.5	119.5	113.5	173.5	175.5	162.5	124.5	164.5	118.5
84.5	189.5	187.5	96.5	193.5	97.5	99.5	203.5	116.5	157.5	155.5	128.5	161.5	129.5	131.5	171.5
85.5	95.5	181.5	104.5	107.5	182.5	192.5	202.5	117.5	127.5	149.5	136.5	139.5	150.5	160.5	170.5
90.5	101.5	110.5	179.5	176.5	109.5	186.5	197.5	122.5	133.5	142.5	147.5	144.5	141.5	154.5	165.5
204.5	103.5	178.5	111.5	108.5	177.5	184.5	83.5	172.5	135.5	146.5	143.5	140.5	145.5	152.5	115.5
199.5	185.5	105.5	180.5	183.5	106.5	102.5	88.5	167.5	153.5	137.5	148.5	151.5	138.5	134.5	120.5
198.5	188.5	100.5	191.5	94.5	190.5	98.5	89.5	166.5	156.5	132.5	159.5	126.5	158.5	130.5	121.5
201.5	206.5	82.5	80.5	93.5	195.5	91.5	200.5	169.5	174.5	114.5	112.5	125.5	163.5	123.5	168.5

Below are details of **magic** and **entries** sums of **block-wise bordered** magic square of order 16. The entries sum is **minimum perfect square**. It is formed by 4 blocks of **bordered** magic squares of order 8 with equal magic sums.

$$S_{16 \times 16} := 2304; \quad T_{256} := 16 \times 2304 = 36864 = 192^2;$$

$$S_{8 \times 8} := 1152; \quad T_{64} := 8 \times 1152 = 9216 = 96^2;$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} := 864; \quad T_{36} := 6 \times 864 = 5184 = 72^2;$$

$$S_{4 \times 4} := 576; \quad T_{16} := 4 \times 576 = 2304 = 48^2;$$

$$T_4 := 576 := 24^2.$$

10 Block-Wise Bordered Magic Square of Order 17

This section brings **bordered** magic square of order 17 resulting in **minimum perfect square sum** of entries.

Example 19. The **block-wise bordered** magic square of order 17 for the **consecutive natural number entries** $\{0, 1, \dots, 287, 288\}$ is given by

273	30	28	26	24	22	20	18	16	276	278	280	282	284	286	288	17
257	243	229	231	233	235	237	239	44	43	41	39	37	35	33	241	31
259	58	71	60	62	64	66	68	216	214	212	210	208	206	215	230	29
261	56	227	93	84	86	88	90	194	192	190	188	186	193	61	232	27
263	54	225	203	175	105	107	109	110	173	171	169	177	85	63	234	25
265	52	223	201	170	161	121	123	124	159	157	163	118	87	65	236	23
267	50	221	199	172	158	153	149	134	133	151	130	116	89	67	238	21
269	48	219	197	174	160	138	141	146	145	150	128	114	91	69	240	19
14	46	218	196	176	162	136	148	144	140	152	126	112	92	70	242	274
13	246	75	97	108	122	156	143	142	147	132	166	180	191	213	42	275
11	248	77	99	106	120	137	139	154	155	135	168	182	189	211	40	277
9	250	79	101	104	125	167	165	164	129	131	127	184	187	209	38	279
7	252	81	103	111	183	181	179	178	115	117	119	113	185	207	36	281
5	254	83	95	204	202	200	198	94	96	98	100	102	195	205	34	283
3	256	73	228	226	224	222	220	72	74	76	78	80	82	217	32	285
1	47	59	57	55	53	51	49	244	245	247	249	251	253	255	45	287
271	258	260	262	264	266	268	270	272	12	10	8	6	4	2	0	15

Below are details of **magic** and **entries** sums of **bordered** magic square of order 17. The entries sum is **minimum perfect square**:

$$S_{17 \times 17} := 2448; \quad T_{289} := 17 \times 2448 = 41616 = 204^2;$$

$$S_{15 \times 15} := 2160; \quad T_{225} := 15 \times 2160 = 32400 = 180^2;$$

$$S_{13 \times 13} := 1872; \quad T_{169} := 13 \times 1872 = 24336 = 156^2;$$

$$S_{11 \times 11} := 1584; \quad T_{121} := 11 \times 1584 = 17424 = 132^2;$$

$$S_{9 \times 9} := 1296; \quad T_{81} := 9 \times 1296 = 11664 = 108^2;$$

$$S_{7 \times 7} := 1008; \quad T_{49} := 7 \times 1008 = 7056 = 84^2;$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} := 720; \quad T_{25} := 5 \times 720 = 3600 = 60^2;$$

$$S_{3 \times 3} := 432; \quad T_9 := 3 \times 432 = 1296 = 36^2;$$

$$T_1 := 144 = 12^2.$$

11 Magic Squares of Order 18

This section brings **bordered** and **block-wise bordered** magic squares of orders 18 resulting in **minimum perfect square sum** of entries.

11.1 Bordered Magic Square of Order 18

Example 20. A *bordered* magic square of order 18 for the *consecutive fraction entries* $\{15/2, 17/2, \dots, 659/2, 661/2\}$ is given by

313.5	31.5	307.5	29.5	309.5	27.5	311.5	25.5	322.5	7.5	315.5	21.5	317.5	19.5	319.5	17.5	321.5	23.5
304.5	281.5	275.5	61.5	277.5	278.5	58.5	57.5	48.5	63.5	283.5	284.5	52.5	286.5	50.5	288.5	55.5	33.5
34.5	64.5	253.5	89.5	249.5	87.5	251.5	85.5	260.5	71.5	255.5	81.5	257.5	79.5	259.5	83.5	273.5	303.5
302.5	272.5	246.5	229.5	225.5	226.5	110.5	109.5	102.5	113.5	231.5	232.5	104.5	234.5	107.5	91.5	65.5	35.5
36.5	66.5	92.5	114.5	209.5	204.5	134.5	202.5	136.5	132.5	122.5	216.5	120.5	210.5	223.5	245.5	271.5	301.5
300.5	270.5	244.5	222.5	131.5	194.5	199.5	139.5	137.5	150.5	188.5	148.5	193.5	206.5	115.5	93.5	67.5	37.5
38.5	68.5	94.5	116.5	207.5	191.5	181.5	157.5	184.5	151.5	183.5	155.5	146.5	130.5	221.5	243.5	269.5	299.5
298.5	268.5	242.5	220.5	129.5	192.5	178.5	174.5	161.5	164.5	175.5	159.5	145.5	208.5	117.5	95.5	69.5	39.5
40.5	70.5	96.5	118.5	214.5	197.5	160.5	167.5	172.5	169.5	166.5	177.5	140.5	123.5	219.5	241.5	267.5	297.5
32.5	41.5	90.5	97.5	119.5	147.5	158.5	171.5	168.5	165.5	170.5	179.5	190.5	218.5	240.5	247.5	296.5	305.5
14.5	47.5	76.5	101.5	211.5	142.5	152.5	162.5	173.5	176.5	163.5	185.5	195.5	126.5	236.5	261.5	290.5	323.5
324.5	291.5	262.5	237.5	125.5	141.5	182.5	180.5	153.5	186.5	154.5	156.5	196.5	212.5	100.5	75.5	46.5	13.5
12.5	45.5	74.5	99.5	213.5	144.5	138.5	198.5	200.5	187.5	149.5	189.5	143.5	124.5	238.5	263.5	292.5	325.5
326.5	293.5	264.5	239.5	127.5	133.5	203.5	135.5	201.5	205.5	215.5	121.5	217.5	128.5	98.5	73.5	44.5	11.5
10.5	43.5	72.5	230.5	112.5	111.5	227.5	228.5	235.5	224.5	106.5	105.5	233.5	103.5	108.5	265.5	294.5	327.5
328.5	295.5	254.5	248.5	88.5	250.5	86.5	252.5	77.5	266.5	82.5	256.5	80.5	258.5	78.5	84.5	42.5	9.5
8.5	282.5	62.5	276.5	60.5	59.5	279.5	280.5	289.5	274.5	54.5	53.5	285.5	51.5	287.5	49.5	56.5	329.5
314.5	306.5	30.5	308.5	28.5	310.5	26.5	312.5	15.5	330.5	22.5	316.5	20.5	318.5	18.5	320.5	16.5	24.5

Below are details of **magic** and **entries** sums of **bordered** magic square of order 18. The entries sum is **minimum perfect square**:

$$S_{18 \times 18} := 3042; \quad T_{324} := 18 \times 3042 = 54756 = 234^2;$$

$$S_{16 \times 16} := 2704; \quad T_{256} := 16 \times 2704 = 43264 = 208^2;$$

$$S_{14 \times 14} := 2366; \quad T_{196} := 14 \times 2366 = 33124 = 182^2;$$

$$S_{12 \times 12} := 2028; \quad T_{144} := 12 \times 2028 = 24336 = 156^2;$$

$$S_{10 \times 10} := 1690; \quad T_{100} := 10 \times 1690 = 16900 = 130^2;$$

$$S_{8 \times 8} := 1352; \quad T_{64} := 8 \times 1352 = 10816 = 104^2;$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} := 1014; \quad T_{36} := 6 \times 1014 = 6084 = 78^2;$$

$$S_{4 \times 4} := 676; \quad T_{16} := 4 \times 676 = 2704 = 52^2;$$

$$T_4 := 676 := 26^2.$$

11.2 Block-Wise Bordered Magic Square of Order 18

Example 21. A *block-wise bordered* magic square of order 18 for the *consecutive fraction entries* $\{15/2, 17/2, \dots, 659/2, 661/2\}$ is given by

326.5	324.5	9.5	330.5	10.5	12.5	308.5	306.5	27.5	312.5	28.5	30.5	290.5	288.5	45.5	294.5	46.5	48.5
8.5	23.5	316.5	17.5	318.5	329.5	26.5	41.5	298.5	35.5	300.5	311.5	44.5	59.5	280.5	53.5	282.5	293.5
14.5	18.5	317.5	24.5	315.5	323.5	32.5	36.5	299.5	42.5	297.5	305.5	50.5	54.5	281.5	60.5	279.5	287.5
16.5	320.5	19.5	314.5	21.5	321.5	34.5	302.5	37.5	296.5	39.5	303.5	52.5	284.5	55.5	278.5	57.5	285.5
322.5	313.5	22.5	319.5	20.5	15.5	304.5	295.5	40.5	301.5	38.5	33.5	286.5	277.5	58.5	283.5	56.5	51.5
325.5	13.5	328.5	7.5	327.5	11.5	307.5	31.5	310.5	25.5	309.5	29.5	289.5	49.5	292.5	43.5	291.5	47.5
272.5	270.5	63.5	276.5	64.5	66.5	254.5	252.5	81.5	258.5	82.5	84.5	236.5	234.5	99.5	240.5	100.5	102.5
62.5	77.5	262.5	71.5	264.5	275.5	80.5	95.5	244.5	89.5	246.5	257.5	98.5	113.5	226.5	107.5	228.5	239.5
68.5	72.5	263.5	78.5	261.5	269.5	86.5	90.5	245.5	96.5	243.5	251.5	104.5	108.5	227.5	114.5	225.5	233.5
70.5	266.5	73.5	260.5	75.5	267.5	88.5	248.5	91.5	242.5	93.5	249.5	106.5	230.5	109.5	224.5	111.5	231.5
268.5	259.5	76.5	265.5	74.5	69.5	250.5	241.5	94.5	247.5	92.5	87.5	232.5	223.5	112.5	229.5	110.5	105.5
271.5	67.5	274.5	61.5	273.5	65.5	253.5	85.5	256.5	79.5	255.5	83.5	235.5	103.5	238.5	97.5	237.5	101.5
218.5	216.5	117.5	222.5	118.5	120.5	200.5	198.5	135.5	204.5	136.5	138.5	182.5	180.5	153.5	186.5	154.5	156.5
116.5	131.5	208.5	125.5	210.5	221.5	134.5	149.5	190.5	143.5	192.5	203.5	152.5	167.5	172.5	161.5	174.5	185.5
122.5	126.5	209.5	132.5	207.5	215.5	140.5	144.5	191.5	150.5	189.5	197.5	158.5	162.5	173.5	168.5	171.5	179.5
124.5	212.5	127.5	206.5	129.5	213.5	142.5	194.5	145.5	188.5	147.5	195.5	160.5	176.5	163.5	170.5	165.5	177.5
214.5	205.5	130.5	211.5	128.5	123.5	196.5	187.5	148.5	193.5	146.5	141.5	178.5	169.5	166.5	175.5	164.5	159.5
217.5	121.5	220.5	115.5	219.5	119.5	199.5	139.5	202.5	133.5	201.5	137.5	181.5	157.5	184.5	151.5	183.5	155.5

Below are details of **magic** and **entries** sums of **block-wise bordered** magic square of order 18. The entries sum is **minimum perfect square**. It is formed by 9 blocks of **bordered** magic squares of order 6 with equal magic sums.

$$S_{18 \times 18} := 3042; \quad T_{324} := 18 \times 3042 = 54756 = 234^2;$$

$$S_{4 \times 4} := 676; \quad T_{16} := 4 \times 676 = 2704 = 52^2;$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} := 1014; \quad T_{36} := 6 \times 1014 = 6084 = 78^2;$$

$$T_4 := 676 := 26^2.$$

12 Bordered Magic Square of Order 19

This section brings **bordered** magic square of order 19 resulting in **minimum perfect square sum** of entries.

Example 22. A *bordered* magic square of order 19 for the *consecutive natural number entries* {16, 17, ..., 375, 376} is given by

359	50	48	46	44	42	40	38	36	34	362	364	366	368	370	372	374	376	35
341	325	82	80	78	76	74	72	70	68	328	330	332	334	336	338	340	69	51
343	309	295	281	283	285	287	289	291	96	95	93	91	89	87	85	293	83	49
345	311	110	123	112	114	116	118	120	268	266	264	262	260	258	267	282	81	47
347	313	108	279	145	136	138	140	142	246	244	242	240	238	245	113	284	79	45
349	315	106	277	255	227	157	159	161	162	225	223	221	229	137	115	286	77	43
351	317	104	275	253	222	213	173	175	176	211	209	215	170	139	117	288	75	41
353	319	102	273	251	224	210	205	201	186	185	203	182	168	141	119	290	73	39
355	321	100	271	249	226	212	190	193	198	197	202	180	166	143	121	292	71	37
32	66	98	270	248	228	214	188	200	196	192	204	178	164	144	122	294	326	360
31	65	298	127	149	160	174	208	195	194	199	184	218	232	243	265	94	327	361
29	63	300	129	151	158	172	189	191	206	207	187	220	234	241	263	92	329	363
27	61	302	131	153	156	177	219	217	216	181	183	179	236	239	261	90	331	365
25	59	304	133	155	163	235	233	231	230	167	169	171	165	237	259	88	333	367
23	57	306	135	147	256	254	252	250	146	148	150	152	154	247	257	86	335	369
21	55	308	125	280	278	276	274	272	124	126	128	130	132	134	269	84	337	371
19	53	99	111	109	107	105	103	101	296	297	299	301	303	305	307	97	339	373
17	323	310	312	314	316	318	320	322	324	64	62	60	58	56	54	52	67	375
357	342	344	346	348	350	352	354	356	358	30	28	26	24	22	20	18	16	33

Below are details of **magic** and **entries** sums of **bordered** magic square of order 19. The entries sum is **minimum perfect square**:

$$S_{19 \times 19} := 3724; \quad T_{361} := 19 \times 3724 = 70756 = 266^2;$$

$$S_{9 \times 9} := 1764; \quad T_{81} := 9 \times 1764 = 15876 = 126^2;$$

$$S_{17 \times 17} := 3332; \quad T_{289} := 17 \times 3332 = 56644 = 238^2;$$

$$S_{7 \times 7} := 1372; \quad T_{49} := 7 \times 1372 = 9604 = 98^2;$$

$$S_{15 \times 15} := 2940; \quad T_{225} := 15 \times 2940 = 44100 = 210^2;$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} := 980; \quad T_{25} := 5 \times 980 = 4900 = 70^2;$$

$$S_{13 \times 13} := 2548; \quad T_{169} := 13 \times 2548 = 33124 = 182^2;$$

$$S_{3 \times 3} := 588; \quad T_9 := 3 \times 588 = 1764 = 42^2;$$

$$S_{11 \times 11} := 2156; \quad T_{121} := 11 \times 2156 = 23716 = 154^2;$$

$$T_1 := 196 = 14^2.$$

13 Magic Squares of Order 20

This section brings **bordered** and **block-wise bordered** magic squares of orders 20 resulting in **minimum perfect square sum** of entries.

13.1 Bordered Magic Square of Order 20

Example 23. A *bordered* magic square of order 18 for the *consecutive fraction entries* $\{51/2, 53/2, \dots, 847/2, 849/2\}$ is given by

405.5	397.5	51.5	399.5	49.5	401.5	402.5	46.5	45.5	34.5	53.5	407.5	408.5	40.5	410.5	38.5	412.5	36.5	414.5	43.5
54.5	369.5	87.5	363.5	85.5	365.5	83.5	367.5	81.5	378.5	63.5	371.5	77.5	373.5	75.5	375.5	73.5	377.5	79.5	395.5
394.5	360.5	337.5	331.5	117.5	333.5	334.5	114.5	113.5	104.5	119.5	339.5	340.5	108.5	342.5	106.5	344.5	111.5	89.5	55.5
56.5	90.5	120.5	309.5	145.5	305.5	143.5	307.5	141.5	316.5	127.5	311.5	137.5	313.5	135.5	315.5	139.5	329.5	359.5	393.5
392.5	358.5	328.5	302.5	285.5	281.5	282.5	166.5	165.5	158.5	169.5	287.5	288.5	160.5	290.5	163.5	147.5	121.5	91.5	57.5
58.5	92.5	122.5	148.5	170.5	265.5	260.5	190.5	258.5	192.5	188.5	178.5	272.5	176.5	266.5	279.5	301.5	327.5	357.5	391.5
390.5	356.5	326.5	300.5	278.5	187.5	250.5	255.5	195.5	193.5	206.5	244.5	204.5	249.5	262.5	171.5	149.5	123.5	93.5	59.5
60.5	94.5	124.5	150.5	172.5	263.5	247.5	237.5	213.5	240.5	207.5	239.5	211.5	202.5	186.5	277.5	299.5	325.5	355.5	389.5
388.5	354.5	324.5	298.5	276.5	185.5	248.5	234.5	230.5	217.5	220.5	231.5	215.5	201.5	264.5	173.5	151.5	125.5	95.5	61.5
62.5	96.5	126.5	152.5	174.5	270.5	253.5	216.5	223.5	228.5	225.5	222.5	233.5	196.5	179.5	275.5	297.5	323.5	353.5	387.5
25.5	88.5	97.5	146.5	153.5	175.5	203.5	214.5	227.5	224.5	221.5	226.5	235.5	246.5	274.5	296.5	303.5	352.5	361.5	424.5
33.5	70.5	103.5	132.5	157.5	267.5	198.5	208.5	218.5	229.5	232.5	219.5	241.5	251.5	182.5	292.5	317.5	346.5	379.5	416.5
417.5	380.5	347.5	318.5	293.5	181.5	197.5	238.5	236.5	209.5	242.5	210.5	212.5	252.5	268.5	156.5	131.5	102.5	69.5	32.5
31.5	68.5	101.5	130.5	155.5	269.5	200.5	194.5	254.5	256.5	243.5	205.5	245.5	199.5	180.5	294.5	319.5	348.5	381.5	418.5
419.5	382.5	349.5	320.5	295.5	183.5	189.5	259.5	191.5	257.5	261.5	271.5	177.5	273.5	184.5	154.5	129.5	100.5	67.5	30.5
29.5	66.5	99.5	128.5	286.5	168.5	167.5	283.5	284.5	291.5	280.5	162.5	161.5	289.5	159.5	164.5	321.5	350.5	383.5	420.5
421.5	384.5	351.5	310.5	304.5	144.5	306.5	142.5	308.5	133.5	322.5	138.5	312.5	136.5	314.5	134.5	140.5	98.5	65.5	28.5
27.5	64.5	338.5	118.5	332.5	116.5	115.5	335.5	336.5	345.5	330.5	110.5	109.5	341.5	107.5	343.5	105.5	112.5	385.5	422.5
423.5	370.5	362.5	86.5	364.5	84.5	366.5	82.5	368.5	71.5	386.5	78.5	372.5	76.5	374.5	74.5	376.5	72.5	80.5	26.5
406.5	52.5	398.5	50.5	400.5	48.5	47.5	403.5	404.5	415.5	396.5	42.5	41.5	409.5	39.5	411.5	37.5	413.5	35.5	44.5

Below are details of **magic** and **entries** sums of **bordered** magic square of order 20. The entries sum is **minimum perfect square**:

$$S_{20 \times 20} := 4500; \quad T_{400} := 20 \times 4500 = 90000 = 300^2;$$

$$S_{18 \times 18} := 4050; \quad T_{324} := 18 \times 4050 = 72900 = 270^2;$$

$$S_{16 \times 16} := 3600; \quad T_{256} := 16 \times 3600 = 57600 = 240^2;$$

$$S_{14 \times 14} := 3150; \quad T_{196} := 14 \times 3150 = 44100 = 210^2;$$

$$S_{12 \times 12} := 2700; \quad T_{144} := 12 \times 2700 = 32400 = 180^2;$$

$$S_{10 \times 10} := 2250; \quad T_{100} := 10 \times 2250 = 22500 = 150^2;$$

$$S_{8 \times 8} := 1800; \quad T_{64} := 8 \times 1800 = 14400 = 120^2;$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} := 1350; \quad T_{36} := 6 \times 1350 = 8100 = 90^2;$$

$$S_{4 \times 4} := 900; \quad T_{16} := 4 \times 900 = 3600 = 60^2;$$

$$T_4 := 900 := 30^2.$$

13.2 Block-Wise Bordered Magic Square of Order 20

Example 24. A *block-wise bordered* magic square of order 18 for the *consecutive fraction entries* $\{51/2, 53/2, \dots, 847/2, 849/2\}$ is given by

415.5	410.5	40.5	408.5	42.5	38.5	28.5	422.5	26.5	416.5	365.5	360.5	90.5	358.5	92.5	88.5	78.5	372.5	76.5	366.5
37.5	50.5	44.5	404.5	406.5	393.5	55.5	395.5	49.5	412.5	87.5	100.5	94.5	354.5	356.5	343.5	105.5	345.5	99.5	362.5
413.5	47.5	388.5	386.5	59.5	392.5	60.5	62.5	402.5	36.5	363.5	97.5	338.5	336.5	109.5	342.5	110.5	112.5	352.5	86.5
35.5	48.5	58.5	380.5	67.5	70.5	381.5	391.5	401.5	414.5	85.5	98.5	108.5	330.5	117.5	120.5	331.5	341.5	351.5	364.5
420.5	53.5	64.5	73.5	378.5	375.5	72.5	385.5	396.5	29.5	370.5	103.5	114.5	123.5	328.5	325.5	122.5	335.5	346.5	79.5
25.5	403.5	66.5	377.5	74.5	71.5	376.5	383.5	46.5	424.5	75.5	353.5	116.5	327.5	124.5	121.5	326.5	333.5	96.5	374.5
417.5	398.5	384.5	68.5	379.5	382.5	69.5	65.5	51.5	32.5	367.5	348.5	334.5	118.5	329.5	332.5	119.5	115.5	101.5	82.5
31.5	397.5	387.5	63.5	390.5	57.5	389.5	61.5	52.5	418.5	81.5	347.5	337.5	113.5	340.5	107.5	339.5	111.5	102.5	368.5
419.5	400.5	405.5	45.5	43.5	56.5	394.5	54.5	399.5	30.5	369.5	350.5	355.5	95.5	93.5	106.5	344.5	104.5	349.5	80.5
33.5	39.5	409.5	41.5	407.5	411.5	421.5	27.5	423.5	34.5	83.5	89.5	359.5	91.5	357.5	361.5	371.5	77.5	373.5	84.5
315.5	310.5	140.5	308.5	142.5	138.5	128.5	322.5	126.5	316.5	265.5	260.5	190.5	258.5	192.5	188.5	178.5	272.5	176.5	266.5
137.5	150.5	144.5	304.5	306.5	293.5	155.5	295.5	149.5	312.5	187.5	200.5	194.5	254.5	256.5	243.5	205.5	245.5	199.5	262.5
313.5	147.5	288.5	286.5	159.5	292.5	160.5	162.5	302.5	136.5	263.5	197.5	238.5	236.5	209.5	242.5	210.5	212.5	252.5	186.5
135.5	148.5	158.5	280.5	167.5	170.5	281.5	291.5	301.5	314.5	185.5	198.5	208.5	230.5	217.5	220.5	231.5	241.5	251.5	264.5
320.5	153.5	164.5	173.5	278.5	275.5	172.5	285.5	296.5	129.5	270.5	203.5	214.5	223.5	228.5	225.5	222.5	235.5	246.5	179.5
125.5	303.5	166.5	277.5	174.5	171.5	276.5	283.5	146.5	324.5	175.5	253.5	216.5	227.5	224.5	221.5	226.5	233.5	196.5	274.5
317.5	298.5	284.5	168.5	279.5	282.5	169.5	165.5	151.5	132.5	267.5	248.5	234.5	218.5	229.5	232.5	219.5	215.5	201.5	182.5
131.5	297.5	287.5	163.5	290.5	157.5	289.5	161.5	152.5	318.5	181.5	247.5	237.5	213.5	240.5	207.5	239.5	211.5	202.5	268.5
319.5	300.5	305.5	145.5	143.5	156.5	294.5	154.5	299.5	130.5	269.5	250.5	255.5	195.5	193.5	206.5	244.5	204.5	249.5	180.5
133.5	139.5	309.5	141.5	307.5	311.5	321.5	127.5	323.5	134.5	183.5	189.5	259.5	191.5	257.5	261.5	271.5	177.5	273.5	184.5

Below are details of **magic** and **entries** sums of **block-wise bordered** magic square of order 20. The entries sum is **minimum perfect square**. It is formed by 4 blocks of **bordered** magic squares of order 10 with equal magic sums.

$$S_{20 \times 20} := 4500; \quad T_{400} := 20 \times 4500 = 90000 = 300^2;$$

$$S_{10 \times 10} := 2250; \quad T_{100} := 10 \times 2250 = 22500 = 150^2;$$

$$S_{8 \times 8} := 1800; \quad T_{64} := 8 \times 1800 = 14400 = 120^2;$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} := 1350; \quad T_{36} := 6 \times 1350 = 8100 = 90^2;$$

$$S_{4 \times 4} := 900; \quad T_{16} := 4 \times 900 = 3600 = 60^2;$$

$$T_4 := 900 = 30^2.$$

14 Bordered Magic Square of Order 21

This section brings **bordered** magic square of order 21 resulting in **minimum perfect square sum** of entries.

Example 25. A *bordered* magic square of order 21 for the *consecutive natural number entries* $\{5, 6, \dots, 444, 445\}$ is given by

424	407	409	411	413	415	417	419	421	423	425	21	19	17	15	13	11	9	7	5	24
6	388	79	77	75	73	71	69	67	65	63	391	393	395	397	399	401	403	405	64	444
8	370	354	111	109	107	105	103	101	99	97	357	359	361	363	365	367	369	98	80	442
10	372	338	324	310	312	314	316	318	320	125	124	122	120	118	116	114	322	112	78	440
12	374	340	139	152	141	143	145	147	149	297	295	293	291	289	287	296	311	110	76	438
14	376	342	137	308	174	165	167	169	171	275	273	271	269	267	274	142	313	108	74	436
16	378	344	135	306	284	256	186	188	190	191	254	252	250	258	166	144	315	106	72	434
18	380	346	133	304	282	251	242	202	204	205	240	238	244	199	168	146	317	104	70	432
20	382	348	131	302	280	253	239	234	230	215	214	232	211	197	170	148	319	102	68	430
22	384	350	129	300	278	255	241	219	222	227	226	231	209	195	172	150	321	100	66	428
23	61	95	127	299	277	257	243	217	229	225	221	233	207	193	173	151	323	355	389	427
422	60	94	327	156	178	189	203	237	224	223	228	213	247	261	272	294	123	356	390	28
420	58	92	329	158	180	187	201	218	220	235	236	216	249	263	270	292	121	358	392	30
418	56	90	331	160	182	185	206	248	246	245	210	212	208	265	268	290	119	360	394	32
416	54	88	333	162	184	192	264	262	260	259	196	198	200	194	266	288	117	362	396	34
414	52	86	335	164	176	285	283	281	279	175	177	179	181	183	276	286	115	364	398	36
412	50	84	337	154	309	307	305	303	301	153	155	157	159	161	163	298	113	366	400	38
410	48	82	128	140	138	136	134	132	130	325	326	328	330	332	334	336	126	368	402	40
408	46	352	339	341	343	345	347	349	351	353	93	91	89	87	85	83	81	96	404	42
406	386	371	373	375	377	379	381	383	385	387	59	57	55	53	51	49	47	45	62	44
426	43	41	39	37	35	33	31	29	27	25	429	431	433	435	437	439	441	443	445	26

Below are details of **magic** and **entries** sums of **bordered** magic square of order 21. The entries sum is **minimum perfect square**:

$$S_{21 \times 21} := 4725; \quad T_{441} := 21 \times 4725 = 99225 = 315^2;$$

$$S_{19 \times 19} := 4275; \quad T_{361} := 19 \times 4275 = 81225 = 285^2;$$

$$S_{17 \times 17} := 3825; \quad T_{289} := 17 \times 3825 = 65025 = 255^2;$$

$$S_{15 \times 15} := 3375; \quad T_{225} := 15 \times 3375 = 50625 = 225^2;$$

$$S_{13 \times 13} := 2925; \quad T_{169} := 13 \times 2925 = 38025 = 195^2;$$

$$S_{11 \times 11} := 2475; \quad T_{121} := 11 \times 2475 = 27225 = 165^2;$$

$$S_{9 \times 9} := 2025; \quad T_{81} := 9 \times 2025 = 18225 = 135^2;$$

$$S_{7 \times 7} := 1575; \quad T_{49} := 7 \times 1575 = 11025 = 105^2;$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} := 1125; \quad T_{25} := 5 \times 1125 = 5625 = 75^2;$$

$$S_{3 \times 3} := 675; \quad T_9 := 3 \times 675 = 2025 = 45^2;$$

$$T_1 := 225 = 15^2.$$

15 Magic Squares of Order 22

This section brings **bordered** and **block-wise bordered** magic squares of orders 22 resulting in **minimum perfect square sum** of entries.

15.1 Bordered Magic Square of Order 22

Example 26. A *bordered* magic square of order 22 for the *consecutive fraction entries* $\{29/2, 31/2, \dots, 993/2, 995/2\}$ is given by

49.5	501.5	41.5	499.5	43.5	497.5	45.5	495.5	47.5	493.5	29.5	502.5	51.5	489.5	53.5	487.5	55.5	485.5	57.5	483.5	59.5	491.5
61.5	451.5	443.5	97.5	445.5	95.5	447.5	448.5	92.5	91.5	80.5	99.5	453.5	454.5	86.5	456.5	84.5	458.5	82.5	460.5	89.5	480.5
479.5	100.5	415.5	133.5	409.5	131.5	411.5	129.5	413.5	127.5	424.5	109.5	417.5	123.5	419.5	121.5	421.5	119.5	423.5	125.5	441.5	62.5
63.5	440.5	406.5	383.5	377.5	163.5	379.5	380.5	160.5	159.5	150.5	165.5	385.5	386.5	154.5	388.5	152.5	390.5	157.5	135.5	101.5	478.5
477.5	102.5	136.5	166.5	355.5	191.5	351.5	189.5	353.5	187.5	362.5	173.5	357.5	183.5	359.5	181.5	361.5	185.5	375.5	405.5	439.5	64.5
65.5	438.5	404.5	374.5	348.5	331.5	327.5	328.5	212.5	211.5	204.5	215.5	333.5	334.5	206.5	336.5	209.5	193.5	167.5	137.5	103.5	476.5
475.5	104.5	138.5	168.5	194.5	216.5	311.5	306.5	236.5	304.5	238.5	234.5	224.5	318.5	222.5	312.5	325.5	347.5	373.5	403.5	437.5	66.5
67.5	436.5	402.5	372.5	346.5	324.5	233.5	296.5	301.5	241.5	239.5	252.5	290.5	250.5	295.5	308.5	217.5	195.5	169.5	139.5	105.5	474.5
473.5	106.5	140.5	170.5	196.5	218.5	309.5	293.5	283.5	259.5	286.5	253.5	285.5	257.5	248.5	232.5	323.5	345.5	371.5	401.5	435.5	68.5
69.5	434.5	400.5	370.5	344.5	322.5	231.5	294.5	280.5	276.5	263.5	266.5	277.5	261.5	247.5	310.5	219.5	197.5	171.5	141.5	107.5	472.5
471.5	108.5	142.5	172.5	198.5	220.5	316.5	299.5	262.5	269.5	274.5	271.5	268.5	279.5	242.5	225.5	321.5	343.5	369.5	399.5	433.5	70.5
481.5	71.5	134.5	143.5	192.5	199.5	221.5	249.5	260.5	273.5	270.5	267.5	272.5	281.5	292.5	320.5	342.5	349.5	398.5	407.5	470.5	60.5
503.5	79.5	116.5	149.5	178.5	203.5	313.5	244.5	254.5	264.5	275.5	278.5	265.5	287.5	297.5	228.5	338.5	363.5	392.5	425.5	462.5	38.5
37.5	463.5	426.5	393.5	364.5	339.5	227.5	243.5	284.5	282.5	255.5	288.5	256.5	258.5	298.5	314.5	202.5	177.5	148.5	115.5	78.5	504.5
505.5	77.5	114.5	147.5	176.5	201.5	315.5	246.5	240.5	300.5	302.5	289.5	251.5	291.5	245.5	226.5	340.5	365.5	394.5	427.5	464.5	36.5
35.5	465.5	428.5	395.5	366.5	341.5	229.5	235.5	305.5	237.5	303.5	307.5	317.5	223.5	319.5	230.5	200.5	175.5	146.5	113.5	76.5	506.5
507.5	75.5	112.5	145.5	174.5	332.5	214.5	213.5	329.5	330.5	337.5	326.5	208.5	207.5	335.5	205.5	210.5	367.5	396.5	429.5	466.5	34.5
33.5	467.5	430.5	397.5	356.5	350.5	190.5	352.5	188.5	354.5	179.5	368.5	184.5	358.5	182.5	360.5	180.5	186.5	144.5	111.5	74.5	508.5
509.5	73.5	110.5	384.5	164.5	378.5	162.5	161.5	381.5	382.5	391.5	376.5	156.5	155.5	387.5	153.5	389.5	151.5	158.5	431.5	468.5	32.5
31.5	469.5	416.5	408.5	132.5	410.5	130.5	412.5	128.5	414.5	117.5	432.5	124.5	418.5	122.5	420.5	120.5	422.5	118.5	126.5	72.5	510.5
511.5	452.5	98.5	444.5	96.5	446.5	94.5	93.5	449.5	450.5	461.5	442.5	88.5	87.5	455.5	85.5	457.5	83.5	459.5	81.5	90.5	30.5
50.5	40.5	500.5	42.5	498.5	44.5	496.5	46.5	494.5	48.5	512.5	39.5	490.5	52.5	488.5	54.5	486.5	56.5	484.5	58.5	482.5	492.5

Below are details of **magic** and **entries** sums of **bordered** magic square of order 22. The entries sum is **minimum perfect square**:

$$S_{22 \times 22} := 5632; \quad T_{484} := 22 \times 5632 = 123904 = 352^2;$$

$$S_{20 \times 20} := 5120; \quad T_{400} := 20 \times 5120 = 102400 = 320^2;$$

$$S_{18 \times 18} := 4608; \quad T_{324} := 18 \times 4608 = 82944 = 288^2;$$

$$S_{16 \times 16} := 4096; \quad T_{256} := 16 \times 4096 = 65536 = 256^2;$$

$$S_{14 \times 14} := 3584; \quad T_{196} := 14 \times 3584 = 50176 = 224^2;$$

$$S_{12 \times 12} := 3072; \quad T_{144} := 12 \times 3072 = 36864 = 192^2;$$

$$S_{10 \times 10} := 2560; \quad T_{100} := 10 \times 2560 = 25600 = 160^2;$$

$$S_{8 \times 8} := 2048; \quad T_{64} := 8 \times 2048 = 16384 = 128^2;$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} := 1536; \quad T_{36} := 6 \times 1536 = 9216 = 96^2;$$

$$S_{4 \times 4} := 1024; \quad T_{16} := 4 \times 1024 = 4096 = 64^2;$$

$$T_4 := 1024 := 32^2.$$

15.2 Block-Wise Bordered Magic Square of Order 22

Example 27. A *block-wise bordered* magic square of order 22 for the *consecutive fraction entries* $\{29/2, 31/2, \dots, 993/2, 995/2\}$ is given by

34.5	486.5	26.5	484.5	28.5	482.5	30.5	480.5	32.5	478.5	14.5	487.5	36.5	474.5	38.5	472.5	40.5	470.5	42.5	468.5	44.5	476.5
46.5	446.5	441.5	71.5	439.5	73.5	69.5	59.5	453.5	57.5	447.5	396.5	391.5	121.5	389.5	123.5	119.5	109.5	403.5	107.5	397.5	465.5
464.5	68.5	81.5	75.5	435.5	437.5	424.5	86.5	426.5	80.5	443.5	118.5	131.5	125.5	385.5	387.5	374.5	136.5	376.5	130.5	393.5	47.5
48.5	444.5	78.5	419.5	417.5	90.5	423.5	91.5	93.5	433.5	67.5	394.5	128.5	369.5	367.5	140.5	373.5	141.5	143.5	383.5	117.5	463.5
462.5	66.5	79.5	89.5	411.5	98.5	101.5	412.5	422.5	432.5	445.5	116.5	129.5	139.5	361.5	148.5	151.5	362.5	372.5	382.5	395.5	49.5
50.5	451.5	84.5	95.5	104.5	409.5	406.5	103.5	416.5	427.5	60.5	401.5	134.5	145.5	154.5	359.5	356.5	153.5	366.5	377.5	110.5	461.5
460.5	56.5	434.5	97.5	408.5	105.5	102.5	407.5	414.5	77.5	455.5	106.5	384.5	147.5	358.5	155.5	152.5	357.5	364.5	127.5	405.5	51.5
52.5	448.5	429.5	415.5	99.5	410.5	413.5	100.5	96.5	82.5	63.5	398.5	379.5	365.5	149.5	360.5	363.5	150.5	146.5	132.5	113.5	459.5
458.5	62.5	428.5	418.5	94.5	421.5	88.5	420.5	92.5	83.5	449.5	112.5	378.5	368.5	144.5	371.5	138.5	370.5	142.5	133.5	399.5	53.5
54.5	450.5	431.5	436.5	76.5	74.5	87.5	425.5	85.5	430.5	61.5	400.5	381.5	386.5	126.5	124.5	137.5	375.5	135.5	380.5	111.5	457.5
456.5	64.5	70.5	440.5	72.5	438.5	442.5	452.5	58.5	454.5	65.5	114.5	120.5	390.5	122.5	388.5	392.5	402.5	108.5	404.5	115.5	55.5
466.5	346.5	341.5	171.5	339.5	173.5	169.5	159.5	353.5	157.5	347.5	296.5	291.5	221.5	289.5	223.5	219.5	209.5	303.5	207.5	297.5	45.5
488.5	168.5	181.5	175.5	335.5	337.5	324.5	186.5	326.5	180.5	343.5	218.5	231.5	225.5	285.5	287.5	274.5	236.5	276.5	230.5	293.5	23.5
22.5	344.5	178.5	319.5	317.5	190.5	323.5	191.5	193.5	333.5	167.5	294.5	228.5	269.5	267.5	240.5	273.5	241.5	243.5	283.5	217.5	489.5
490.5	166.5	179.5	189.5	311.5	198.5	201.5	312.5	322.5	332.5	345.5	216.5	229.5	239.5	261.5	248.5	251.5	262.5	272.5	282.5	295.5	21.5
20.5	351.5	184.5	195.5	204.5	309.5	306.5	203.5	316.5	327.5	160.5	301.5	234.5	245.5	254.5	259.5	256.5	253.5	266.5	277.5	210.5	491.5
492.5	156.5	334.5	197.5	308.5	205.5	202.5	307.5	314.5	177.5	355.5	206.5	284.5	247.5	258.5	255.5	252.5	257.5	264.5	227.5	305.5	19.5
18.5	348.5	329.5	315.5	199.5	310.5	313.5	200.5	196.5	182.5	163.5	298.5	279.5	265.5	249.5	260.5	263.5	250.5	246.5	232.5	213.5	493.5
494.5	162.5	328.5	318.5	194.5	321.5	188.5	320.5	192.5	183.5	349.5	212.5	278.5	268.5	244.5	271.5	238.5	270.5	242.5	233.5	299.5	17.5
16.5	350.5	331.5	336.5	176.5	174.5	187.5	325.5	185.5	330.5	161.5	300.5	281.5	286.5	226.5	224.5	237.5	275.5	235.5	280.5	211.5	495.5
496.5	164.5	170.5	340.5	172.5	338.5	342.5	352.5	158.5	354.5	165.5	214.5	220.5	290.5	222.5	288.5	292.5	302.5	208.5	304.5	215.5	15.5
35.5	25.5	485.5	27.5	483.5	29.5	481.5	31.5	479.5	33.5	497.5	24.5	475.5	37.5	473.5	39.5	471.5	41.5	469.5	43.5	467.5	477.5

Below are details of **magic** and **entries** sums of **block-wise bordered** magic square of order 22. The entries sum is **minimum perfect square**. It is formed by inner block of magic square of order 20 with 4 blocks of **bordered** magic squares of order 10 with equal magic sums.

$$S_{22 \times 22} := 5632; \quad T_{484} := 22 \times 5632 = 123904 = 352^2;$$

$$S_{20 \times 20} := 5120; \quad T_{400} := 20 \times 5120 = 102400 = 320^2;$$

$$S_{10 \times 10} := 2560; \quad T_{100} := 10 \times 2560 = 25600 = 160^2;$$

$$S_{8 \times 8} := 2048; \quad T_{64} := 8 \times 2048 = 16384 = 128^2;$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} := 1536; \quad T_{36} := 6 \times 1536 = 9216 = 96^2;$$

$$S_{4 \times 4} := 1024; \quad T_{16} := 4 \times 1024 = 4096 = 64^2;$$

$$T_4 := 1024 := 32^2.$$

16 Bordered Magic Square of Order 23

This section brings **bordered** magic square of order 23 resulting in **minimum perfect square sum** of entries.

Example 28. A *bordered* magic square of order 23 for the *consecutive natural number entries* {25, 26, ..., 552, 553} is given by

532	67	65	63	61	59	57	55	53	51	49	47	535	537	539	541	543	545	547	549	551	553	48
510	488	471	473	475	477	479	481	483	485	487	489	85	83	81	79	77	75	73	71	69	88	68
512	70	452	143	141	139	137	135	133	131	129	127	455	457	459	461	463	465	467	469	128	508	66
514	72	434	418	175	173	171	169	167	165	163	161	421	423	425	427	429	431	433	162	144	506	64
516	74	436	402	388	374	376	378	380	382	384	189	188	186	184	182	180	178	386	176	142	504	62
518	76	438	404	203	216	205	207	209	211	213	361	359	357	355	353	351	360	375	174	140	502	60
520	78	440	406	201	372	238	229	231	233	235	339	337	335	333	331	338	206	377	172	138	500	58
522	80	442	408	199	370	348	320	250	252	254	255	318	316	314	322	230	208	379	170	136	498	56
524	82	444	410	197	368	346	315	306	266	268	269	304	302	308	263	232	210	381	168	134	496	54
526	84	446	412	195	366	344	317	303	298	294	279	278	296	275	261	234	212	383	166	132	494	52
528	86	448	414	193	364	342	319	305	283	286	291	290	295	273	259	236	214	385	164	130	492	50
45	87	125	159	191	363	341	321	307	281	293	289	285	297	271	257	237	215	387	419	453	491	533
44	486	124	158	391	220	242	253	267	301	288	287	292	277	311	325	336	358	187	420	454	92	534
42	484	122	156	393	222	244	251	265	282	284	299	300	280	313	327	334	356	185	422	456	94	536
40	482	120	154	395	224	246	249	270	312	310	309	274	276	272	329	332	354	183	424	458	96	538
38	480	118	152	397	226	248	256	328	326	324	323	260	262	264	258	330	352	181	426	460	98	540
36	478	116	150	399	228	240	349	347	345	343	239	241	243	245	247	340	350	179	428	462	100	542
34	476	114	148	401	218	373	371	369	367	365	217	219	221	223	225	227	362	177	430	464	102	544
32	474	112	146	192	204	202	200	198	196	194	389	390	392	394	396	398	400	190	432	466	104	546
30	472	110	416	403	405	407	409	411	413	415	417	157	155	153	151	149	147	145	160	468	106	548
28	470	450	435	437	439	441	443	445	447	449	451	123	121	119	117	115	113	111	109	126	108	550
26	490	107	105	103	101	99	97	95	93	91	89	493	495	497	499	501	503	505	507	509	90	552
530	511	513	515	517	519	521	523	525	527	529	531	43	41	39	37	35	33	31	29	27	25	46

Below are details of **magic** and **entries** sums of **bordered** magic square of order 23. The entries sum is **minimum perfect square**:

$$S_{23 \times 23} := 6647; \quad T_{529} := 23 \times 6647 = 152881 = 391^2;$$

$$S_{21 \times 21} := 6069; \quad T_{441} := 21 \times 6069 = 127449 = 357^2;$$

$$S_{19 \times 19} := 5491; \quad T_{361} := 19 \times 5491 = 104329 = 323^2;$$

$$S_{17 \times 17} := 4913; \quad T_{289} := 17 \times 4913 = 83521 = 289^2;$$

$$S_{15 \times 15} := 4335; \quad T_{225} := 15 \times 4335 = 65025 = 255^2;$$

$$S_{13 \times 13} := 3757; \quad T_{169} := 13 \times 3757 = 48841 = 221^2;$$

$$S_{11 \times 11} := 3179; \quad T_{121} := 11 \times 3179 = 34969 = 187^2;$$

$$S_{9 \times 9} := 2601; \quad T_{81} := 9 \times 2601 = 23409 = 153^2;$$

$$S_{7 \times 7} := 2023; \quad T_{49} := 7 \times 2023 = 14161 = 119^2;$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} := 1445; \quad T_{25} := 5 \times 1445 = 7225 = 85^2;$$

$$S_{3 \times 3} := 867; \quad T_9 := 3 \times 867 = 2601 = 51^2;$$

$$T_1 := 289 = 17^2.$$

17 Magic Squares of Order 24

This section brings **bordered** and **block-wise bordered** magic squares of orders 24 resulting in **minimum perfect square sum** of entries.

17.1 Bordered Magic Square of Order 24

Example 29. A *block-wise bordered* magic square of order 24 for the *consecutive fraction entries* $\{3/2, 5/2, \dots, 1151/2, 1153/2\}$ is given by

554.5	34.5	544.5	32.5	546.5	30.5	548.5	28.5	27.5	551.5	552.5	565.5	542.5	22.5	21.5	557.5	19.5	559.5	17.5	561.5	15.5	563.5	13.5	24.5
575.5	67.5	519.5	59.5	517.5	61.5	515.5	63.5	513.5	65.5	511.5	47.5	520.5	69.5	507.5	71.5	505.5	73.5	503.5	75.5	501.5	77.5	509.5	2.5
3.5	79.5	469.5	461.5	115.5	463.5	113.5	465.5	466.5	110.5	109.5	98.5	117.5	471.5	472.5	104.5	474.5	102.5	476.5	100.5	478.5	107.5	498.5	574.5
573.5	497.5	118.5	433.5	151.5	427.5	149.5	429.5	147.5	431.5	145.5	442.5	127.5	435.5	141.5	437.5	139.5	439.5	137.5	441.5	143.5	459.5	80.5	4.5
5.5	81.5	458.5	424.5	401.5	395.5	181.5	397.5	398.5	178.5	177.5	168.5	183.5	403.5	404.5	172.5	406.5	170.5	408.5	175.5	153.5	119.5	496.5	572.5
571.5	495.5	120.5	154.5	184.5	373.5	209.5	369.5	207.5	371.5	205.5	380.5	191.5	375.5	201.5	377.5	199.5	379.5	203.5	393.5	423.5	457.5	82.5	6.5
7.5	83.5	456.5	422.5	392.5	366.5	349.5	345.5	346.5	230.5	229.5	222.5	233.5	351.5	352.5	224.5	354.5	227.5	211.5	185.5	155.5	121.5	494.5	570.5
569.5	493.5	122.5	156.5	186.5	212.5	234.5	329.5	324.5	254.5	322.5	256.5	252.5	242.5	336.5	240.5	330.5	343.5	365.5	391.5	421.5	455.5	84.5	8.5
9.5	85.5	454.5	420.5	390.5	364.5	342.5	251.5	314.5	319.5	259.5	257.5	270.5	308.5	268.5	313.5	326.5	235.5	213.5	187.5	157.5	123.5	492.5	568.5
567.5	491.5	124.5	158.5	188.5	214.5	236.5	327.5	311.5	301.5	277.5	304.5	271.5	303.5	275.5	266.5	250.5	341.5	363.5	389.5	419.5	453.5	86.5	10.5
11.5	87.5	452.5	418.5	388.5	362.5	340.5	249.5	312.5	298.5	294.5	281.5	284.5	295.5	279.5	265.5	328.5	237.5	215.5	189.5	159.5	125.5	490.5	566.5
1.5	489.5	126.5	160.5	190.5	216.5	238.5	334.5	317.5	280.5	287.5	292.5	289.5	286.5	297.5	260.5	243.5	339.5	361.5	387.5	417.5	451.5	88.5	576.5
46.5	499.5	89.5	152.5	161.5	210.5	217.5	239.5	267.5	278.5	291.5	288.5	285.5	290.5	299.5	310.5	338.5	360.5	367.5	416.5	425.5	488.5	78.5	531.5
532.5	521.5	97.5	134.5	167.5	196.5	221.5	331.5	262.5	272.5	282.5	293.5	296.5	283.5	305.5	315.5	246.5	356.5	381.5	410.5	443.5	480.5	56.5	45.5
44.5	55.5	481.5	444.5	411.5	382.5	357.5	245.5	261.5	302.5	300.5	273.5	306.5	274.5	276.5	316.5	332.5	220.5	195.5	166.5	133.5	96.5	522.5	533.5
534.5	523.5	95.5	132.5	165.5	194.5	219.5	333.5	264.5	258.5	318.5	320.5	307.5	269.5	309.5	263.5	244.5	358.5	383.5	412.5	445.5	482.5	54.5	43.5
42.5	53.5	483.5	446.5	413.5	384.5	359.5	247.5	253.5	323.5	255.5	321.5	325.5	335.5	241.5	337.5	248.5	218.5	193.5	164.5	131.5	94.5	524.5	535.5
536.5	525.5	93.5	130.5	163.5	192.5	350.5	232.5	231.5	347.5	348.5	355.5	344.5	226.5	225.5	353.5	223.5	228.5	385.5	414.5	447.5	484.5	52.5	41.5
40.5	51.5	485.5	448.5	415.5	374.5	368.5	208.5	370.5	206.5	372.5	197.5	386.5	202.5	376.5	200.5	378.5	198.5	204.5	162.5	129.5	92.5	526.5	537.5
538.5	527.5	91.5	128.5	402.5	182.5	396.5	180.5	179.5	399.5	400.5	409.5	394.5	174.5	173.5	405.5	171.5	407.5	169.5	176.5	449.5	486.5	50.5	39.5
38.5	49.5	487.5	434.5	426.5	150.5	428.5	148.5	430.5	146.5	432.5	135.5	450.5	142.5	436.5	140.5	438.5	138.5	440.5	136.5	144.5	90.5	528.5	539.5
540.5	529.5	470.5	116.5	462.5	114.5	464.5	112.5	111.5	467.5	468.5	479.5	460.5	106.5	105.5	473.5	103.5	475.5	101.5	477.5	99.5	108.5	48.5	37.5
36.5	68.5	58.5	518.5	60.5	516.5	62.5	514.5	64.5	512.5	66.5	530.5	57.5	508.5	70.5	506.5	72.5	504.5	74.5	502.5	76.5	500.5	510.5	541.5
553.5	543.5	33.5	545.5	31.5	547.5	29.5	549.5	550.5	26.5	25.5	12.5	35.5	555.5	556.5	20.5	558.5	18.5	560.5	16.5	562.5	14.5	564.5	23.5

Below are details of **magic** and **entries** sums of **bordered** magic square of order 24. The entries sum is **minimum perfect square**:

$$S_{24 \times 24} := 6936; \quad T_{576} := 24 \times 6936 = 166464 = 408^2;$$

$$S_{22 \times 22} := 6358; \quad T_{484} := 22 \times 6358 = 139876 = 374^2;$$

$$S_{20 \times 20} := 5780; \quad T_{400} := 20 \times 5780 = 115600 = 340^2;$$

$$S_{18 \times 18} := 5202; \quad T_{324} := 18 \times 5202 = 93636 = 306^2;$$

$$S_{16 \times 16} := 4624; \quad T_{256} := 16 \times 4624 = 73984 = 272^2;$$

$$S_{14 \times 14} := 4046; \quad T_{196} := 14 \times 4046 = 56644 = 238^2;$$

$$S_{12 \times 12} := 3468; \quad T_{144} := 12 \times 3468 = 41616 = 204^2;$$

$$S_{10 \times 10} := 2890; \quad T_{100} := 10 \times 2890 = 28900 = 170^2;$$

$$S_{8 \times 8} := 2312; \quad T_{64} := 8 \times 2312 = 18496 = 136^2;$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} := 1734; \quad T_{36} := 6 \times 1734 = 10404 = 102^2;$$

$$S_{4 \times 4} := 1156; \quad T_{16} := 4 \times 1156 = 4624 = 68^2;$$

$$T_4 := 1156 := 34^2.$$

17.2 Block-Wise Bordered Magic Square of Order 24

Example 30. A *block-wise bordered* magic square of order 24 for the *consecutive fraction entries* $\{3/2, 5/2, \dots, 1151/2, 1153/2\}$ is given by

566.5	575.5	3.5	573.5	5.5	1.5	22.5	556.5	20.5	558.5	18.5	565.5	494.5	503.5	75.5	501.5	77.5	73.5	94.5	484.5	92.5	486.5	90.5	493.5
16.5	545.5	540.5	38.5	538.5	40.5	36.5	26.5	552.5	24.5	546.5	561.5	88.5	473.5	468.5	110.5	466.5	112.5	108.5	98.5	480.5	96.5	474.5	489.5
15.5	35.5	48.5	42.5	534.5	536.5	523.5	53.5	525.5	47.5	542.5	562.5	87.5	107.5	120.5	114.5	462.5	464.5	451.5	125.5	453.5	119.5	470.5	490.5
563.5	543.5	45.5	518.5	516.5	57.5	522.5	58.5	60.5	532.5	34.5	14.5	491.5	471.5	117.5	446.5	444.5	129.5	450.5	130.5	132.5	460.5	106.5	86.5
564.5	33.5	46.5	56.5	510.5	65.5	68.5	511.5	521.5	531.5	544.5	13.5	492.5	105.5	118.5	128.5	438.5	137.5	140.5	439.5	449.5	459.5	472.5	85.5
571.5	550.5	51.5	62.5	71.5	508.5	505.5	70.5	515.5	526.5	27.5	6.5	499.5	478.5	123.5	134.5	143.5	436.5	433.5	142.5	443.5	454.5	99.5	78.5
560.5	23.5	533.5	64.5	507.5	72.5	69.5	506.5	513.5	44.5	554.5	17.5	488.5	95.5	461.5	136.5	435.5	144.5	141.5	434.5	441.5	116.5	482.5	89.5
10.5	547.5	528.5	514.5	66.5	509.5	512.5	67.5	63.5	49.5	30.5	567.5	82.5	475.5	456.5	442.5	138.5	437.5	440.5	139.5	135.5	121.5	102.5	495.5
9.5	29.5	527.5	517.5	61.5	520.5	55.5	519.5	59.5	50.5	548.5	568.5	81.5	101.5	455.5	445.5	133.5	448.5	127.5	447.5	131.5	122.5	476.5	496.5
569.5	549.5	530.5	535.5	43.5	41.5	54.5	524.5	52.5	529.5	28.5	8.5	497.5	477.5	458.5	463.5	115.5	113.5	126.5	452.5	124.5	457.5	100.5	80.5
7.5	31.5	37.5	539.5	39.5	537.5	541.5	551.5	25.5	553.5	32.5	570.5	79.5	103.5	109.5	467.5	111.5	465.5	469.5	479.5	97.5	481.5	104.5	498.5
12.5	2.5	574.5	4.5	572.5	576.5	555.5	21.5	557.5	19.5	559.5	11.5	84.5	74.5	502.5	76.5	500.5	504.5	483.5	93.5	485.5	91.5	487.5	83.5
422.5	431.5	147.5	429.5	149.5	145.5	166.5	412.5	164.5	414.5	162.5	421.5	350.5	359.5	219.5	357.5	221.5	217.5	238.5	340.5	236.5	342.5	234.5	349.5
160.5	401.5	396.5	182.5	394.5	184.5	180.5	170.5	408.5	168.5	402.5	417.5	232.5	329.5	324.5	254.5	322.5	256.5	252.5	242.5	336.5	240.5	330.5	345.5
159.5	179.5	192.5	186.5	390.5	392.5	379.5	197.5	381.5	191.5	398.5	418.5	231.5	251.5	264.5	258.5	318.5	320.5	307.5	269.5	309.5	263.5	326.5	346.5
419.5	399.5	189.5	374.5	372.5	201.5	378.5	202.5	204.5	388.5	178.5	158.5	347.5	327.5	261.5	302.5	300.5	273.5	306.5	274.5	276.5	316.5	250.5	230.5
420.5	177.5	190.5	200.5	366.5	209.5	212.5	367.5	377.5	387.5	400.5	157.5	348.5	249.5	262.5	272.5	294.5	281.5	284.5	295.5	305.5	315.5	328.5	229.5
427.5	406.5	195.5	206.5	215.5	364.5	361.5	214.5	371.5	382.5	171.5	150.5	355.5	334.5	267.5	278.5	287.5	292.5	289.5	286.5	299.5	310.5	243.5	222.5
416.5	167.5	389.5	208.5	363.5	216.5	213.5	362.5	369.5	188.5	410.5	161.5	344.5	239.5	317.5	280.5	291.5	288.5	285.5	290.5	297.5	260.5	338.5	233.5
154.5	403.5	384.5	370.5	210.5	365.5	368.5	211.5	207.5	193.5	174.5	423.5	226.5	331.5	312.5	298.5	282.5	293.5	296.5	283.5	279.5	265.5	246.5	351.5
153.5	173.5	383.5	373.5	205.5	376.5	199.5	375.5	203.5	194.5	404.5	424.5	225.5	245.5	311.5	301.5	277.5	304.5	271.5	303.5	275.5	266.5	332.5	352.5
425.5	405.5	386.5	391.5	187.5	185.5	198.5	380.5	196.5	385.5	172.5	152.5	353.5	333.5	314.5	319.5	259.5	257.5	270.5	308.5	268.5	313.5	244.5	224.5
151.5	175.5	181.5	395.5	183.5	393.5	397.5	407.5	169.5	409.5	176.5	426.5	223.5	247.5	253.5	323.5	255.5	321.5	325.5	335.5	241.5	337.5	248.5	354.5
156.5	146.5	430.5	148.5	428.5	432.5	411.5	165.5	413.5	163.5	415.5	155.5	228.5	218.5	358.5	220.5	356.5	360.5	339.5	237.5	341.5	235.5	343.5	227.5

Below are details of **magic** and **entries** sums of **block-wise bordered** magic square of order 24. The entries sum is **minimum perfect square**. It is formed by 4 blocks of **bordered** magic squares of order 12 with equal magic sums.

$$S_{24 \times 24} := 6936; \quad T_{576} := 24 \times 6936 = 166464 = 408^2;$$

$$S_{12 \times 12} := 3468; \quad T_{144} := 12 \times 3468 = 41616 = 204^2;$$

$$S_{10 \times 10} := 2890; \quad T_{100} := 10 \times 2890 = 28900 = 170^2;$$

$$S_{8 \times 8} := 2312; \quad T_{64} := 8 \times 2312 = 18496 = 136^2;$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} := 1734; \quad T_{36} := 6 \times 1734 = 10404 = 102^2;$$

$$S_{4 \times 4} := 1156; \quad T_{16} := 4 \times 1156 = 4624 = 68^2;$$

$$T_4 := 1156 := 34^2.$$

18 Bordered Magic Square of Order 25

This section brings **bordered** magic square of order 25 resulting in **minimum perfect square sum** of entries.

Example 31. A *bordered* magic square of order 25 for the *consecutive natural number entries* {12, 13, ..., 635, 636} is given by

37	636	634	632	630	628	626	624	622	620	618	616	36	38	40	42	44	46	48	50	52	54	56	58	613
59	567	102	100	98	96	94	92	90	88	86	84	82	570	572	574	576	578	580	582	584	586	588	83	589
57	545	523	506	508	510	512	514	516	518	520	522	524	120	118	116	114	112	110	108	106	104	123	103	591
55	547	105	487	178	176	174	172	170	168	166	164	162	490	492	494	496	498	500	502	504	163	543	101	593
53	549	107	469	453	210	208	206	204	202	200	198	196	456	458	460	462	464	466	468	197	179	541	99	595
51	551	109	471	437	423	409	411	413	415	417	419	224	223	221	219	217	215	213	421	211	177	539	97	597
49	553	111	473	439	238	251	240	242	244	246	248	396	394	392	390	388	386	395	410	209	175	537	95	599
47	555	113	475	441	236	407	273	264	266	268	270	374	372	370	368	366	373	241	412	207	173	535	93	601
45	557	115	477	443	234	405	383	355	285	287	289	290	353	351	349	357	265	243	414	205	171	533	91	603
43	559	117	479	445	232	403	381	350	341	301	303	304	339	337	343	298	267	245	416	203	169	531	89	605
41	561	119	481	447	230	401	379	352	338	333	329	314	313	331	310	296	269	247	418	201	167	529	87	607
39	563	121	483	449	228	399	377	354	340	318	321	326	325	330	308	294	271	249	420	199	165	527	85	609
614	80	122	160	194	226	398	376	356	342	316	328	324	320	332	306	292	272	250	422	454	488	526	568	34
615	79	521	159	193	426	255	277	288	302	336	323	322	327	312	346	360	371	393	222	455	489	127	569	33
617	77	519	157	191	428	257	279	286	300	317	319	334	335	315	348	362	369	391	220	457	491	129	571	31
619	75	517	155	189	430	259	281	284	305	347	345	344	309	311	307	364	367	389	218	459	493	131	573	29
621	73	515	153	187	432	261	283	291	363	361	359	358	295	297	299	293	365	387	216	461	495	133	575	27
623	71	513	151	185	434	263	275	384	382	380	378	274	276	278	280	282	375	385	214	463	497	135	577	25
625	69	511	149	183	436	253	408	406	404	402	400	252	254	256	258	260	262	397	212	465	499	137	579	23
627	67	509	147	181	227	239	237	235	233	231	229	424	425	427	429	431	433	435	225	467	501	139	581	21
629	65	507	145	451	438	440	442	444	446	448	450	452	192	190	188	186	184	182	180	195	503	141	583	19
631	63	505	485	470	472	474	476	478	480	482	484	486	158	156	154	152	150	148	146	144	161	143	585	17
633	61	525	142	140	138	136	134	132	130	128	126	124	528	530	532	534	536	538	540	542	544	125	587	15
635	565	546	548	550	552	554	556	558	560	562	564	566	78	76	74	72	70	68	66	64	62	60	81	13
35	12	14	16	18	20	22	24	26	28	30	32	612	610	608	606	604	602	600	598	596	594	592	590	611

Below are details of **magic** and **entries** sums of **bordered** magic square of order 25. The entries sum is **minimum perfect square**:

$$S_{25 \times 25} := 8100; \quad T_{625} := 25 \times 8100 = 202500 = 450^2;$$

$$S_{23 \times 23} := 7452; \quad T_{529} := 23 \times 7452 = 171396 = 414^2;$$

$$S_{21 \times 21} := 6804; \quad T_{441} := 21 \times 6804 = 142884 = 378^2;$$

$$S_{19 \times 19} := 6156; \quad T_{361} := 19 \times 6156 = 116964 = 342^2;$$

$$S_{17 \times 17} := 5508; \quad T_{289} := 17 \times 5508 = 93636 = 306^2;$$

$$S_{15 \times 15} := 4860; \quad T_{225} := 15 \times 4860 = 72900 = 270^2;$$

$$S_{13 \times 13} := 4212; \quad T_{169} := 13 \times 4212 = 54756 = 234^2;$$

$$S_{11 \times 11} := 3564; \quad T_{121} := 11 \times 3564 = 39204 = 198^2;$$

$$S_{9 \times 9} := 2916; \quad T_{81} := 9 \times 2916 = 26244 = 162^2;$$

$$S_{7 \times 7} := 2268; \quad T_{49} := 7 \times 2268 = 15876 = 126^2;$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} := 1620; \quad T_{25} := 5 \times 1620 = 8100 = 90^2;$$

$$S_{3 \times 3} := 972; \quad T_9 := 3 \times 972 = 2916 = 54^2;$$

$$T_1 := 324 = 18^2.$$

19 Magic Squares of Order 26

This section brings **bordered** and **block-wise bordered** magic squares of orders 26 resulting in **minimum perfect square sum** of entries.

19.1 Bordered Magic Square of Order 26

Example 32. A bordered magic square of order 26 for the consecutive fraction entries $\{47/2, 49/2, \dots, 1395/2, 1397/2\}$ is given by

47.5	685.5	37.5	683.5	39.5	681.5	41.5	679.5	43.5	677.5	45.5	675.5	23.5	686.5	49.5	671.5	51.5	669.5	53.5	667.5	55.5	665.5	57.5	663.5	59.5	673.5
61.5	96.5	85.5	635.5	87.5	633.5	89.5	631.5	91.5	629.5	93.5	94.5	614.5	637.5	624.5	623.5	99.5	100.5	620.5	102.5	618.5	104.5	616.5	106.5	626.5	660.5
659.5	74.5	581.5	570.5	152.5	568.5	154.5	566.5	156.5	564.5	158.5	562.5	160.5	150.5	128.5	594.5	126.5	596.5	124.5	598.5	122.5	600.5	120.5	582.5	647.5	62.5
63.5	646.5	149.5	179.5	550.5	172.5	548.5	174.5	546.5	176.5	544.5	543.5	189.5	170.5	181.5	182.5	538.5	537.5	185.5	535.5	187.5	533.5	541.5	572.5	75.5	658.5
657.5	76.5	573.5	531.5	505.5	223.5	499.5	221.5	501.5	219.5	503.5	217.5	514.5	199.5	507.5	213.5	509.5	211.5	511.5	209.5	513.5	215.5	190.5	148.5	645.5	64.5
65.5	644.5	147.5	191.5	496.5	247.5	465.5	257.5	463.5	259.5	461.5	261.5	459.5	488.5	482.5	238.5	484.5	236.5	486.5	234.5	248.5	225.5	530.5	574.5	77.5	656.5
655.5	78.5	575.5	529.5	226.5	480.5	275.5	451.5	271.5	449.5	273.5	447.5	263.5	452.5	277.5	443.5	279.5	441.5	281.5	445.5	241.5	495.5	192.5	146.5	643.5	66.5
67.5	642.5	145.5	193.5	494.5	242.5	283.5	422.5	304.5	303.5	419.5	420.5	427.5	416.5	298.5	297.5	425.5	295.5	300.5	438.5	479.5	227.5	528.5	576.5	79.5	654.5
653.5	80.5	577.5	527.5	228.5	478.5	437.5	431.5	402.5	398.5	322.5	400.5	315.5	410.5	318.5	404.5	316.5	320.5	290.5	284.5	243.5	493.5	194.5	144.5	641.5	68.5
69.5	640.5	143.5	195.5	492.5	244.5	285.5	291.5	312.5	385.5	338.5	337.5	332.5	382.5	387.5	388.5	335.5	409.5	430.5	436.5	477.5	229.5	526.5	578.5	81.5	652.5
651.5	82.5	579.5	525.5	230.5	476.5	435.5	429.5	408.5	340.5	374.5	372.5	345.5	378.5	346.5	348.5	381.5	313.5	292.5	286.5	245.5	491.5	196.5	142.5	639.5	70.5
71.5	638.5	141.5	197.5	490.5	475.5	287.5	293.5	314.5	380.5	344.5	354.5	363.5	359.5	366.5	377.5	341.5	407.5	428.5	434.5	246.5	231.5	524.5	580.5	83.5	650.5
649.5	648.5	592.5	523.5	232.5	255.5	433.5	289.5	324.5	342.5	350.5	365.5	360.5	364.5	353.5	371.5	379.5	397.5	432.5	288.5	466.5	489.5	198.5	129.5	73.5	72.5
661.5	603.5	119.5	560.5	224.5	240.5	439.5	310.5	328.5	329.5	352.5	368.5	357.5	361.5	356.5	369.5	392.5	393.5	411.5	282.5	481.5	497.5	161.5	602.5	118.5	60.5
687.5	117.5	583.5	552.5	206.5	249.5	453.5	412.5	394.5	331.5	370.5	355.5	362.5	358.5	367.5	351.5	390.5	327.5	309.5	268.5	472.5	515.5	169.5	138.5	604.5	34.5
33.5	605.5	137.5	168.5	516.5	250.5	267.5	308.5	326.5	391.5	373.5	349.5	376.5	343.5	375.5	347.5	330.5	395.5	413.5	454.5	471.5	205.5	553.5	584.5	116.5	688.5
689.5	115.5	585.5	554.5	204.5	470.5	455.5	414.5	396.5	386.5	383.5	384.5	389.5	339.5	334.5	333.5	336.5	325.5	307.5	266.5	251.5	517.5	167.5	136.5	606.5	32.5
31.5	607.5	135.5	166.5	518.5	469.5	265.5	306.5	401.5	323.5	399.5	321.5	406.5	311.5	403.5	317.5	405.5	319.5	415.5	456.5	252.5	203.5	555.5	586.5	114.5	690.5
691.5	113.5	587.5	556.5	202.5	253.5	457.5	421.5	417.5	418.5	302.5	301.5	294.5	305.5	423.5	424.5	296.5	426.5	299.5	264.5	468.5	519.5	165.5	134.5	608.5	30.5
29.5	609.5	133.5	164.5	520.5	467.5	276.5	270.5	450.5	272.5	448.5	274.5	458.5	269.5	444.5	278.5	442.5	280.5	440.5	446.5	254.5	201.5	557.5	588.5	112.5	692.5
693.5	111.5	589.5	558.5	200.5	473.5	256.5	464.5	258.5	462.5	260.5	460.5	262.5	233.5	239.5	483.5	237.5	485.5	235.5	487.5	474.5	521.5	163.5	132.5	610.5	28.5
27.5	611.5	131.5	162.5	506.5	498.5	222.5	500.5	220.5	502.5	218.5	504.5	207.5	522.5	214.5	508.5	212.5	510.5	210.5	512.5	208.5	216.5	559.5	590.5	110.5	694.5
695.5	109.5	591.5	180.5	171.5	549.5	173.5	547.5	175.5	545.5	177.5	178.5	532.5	551.5	540.5	539.5	183.5	184.5	536.5	186.5	534.5	188.5	542.5	130.5	612.5	26.5
25.5	613.5	139.5	151.5	569.5	153.5	567.5	155.5	565.5	157.5	563.5	159.5	561.5	571.5	593.5	127.5	595.5	125.5	597.5	123.5	599.5	121.5	601.5	140.5	108.5	696.5
697.5	95.5	636.5	86.5	634.5	88.5	632.5	90.5	630.5	92.5	628.5	627.5	107.5	84.5	97.5	98.5	622.5	621.5	101.5	619.5	103.5	617.5	105.5	615.5	625.5	24.5
48.5	36.5	684.5	38.5	682.5	40.5	680.5	42.5	678.5	44.5	676.5	46.5	698.5	35.5	672.5	50.5	670.5	52.5	668.5	54.5	666.5	56.5	664.5	58.5	662.5	674.5

Below are details of **magic** and **entries** sums of **bordered** magic square of order 26. The entries sum is **minimum perfect square**:

$$S_{26 \times 26} := 9386; \quad T_{676} := 26 \times 9386 = 244036 = 494^2;$$

$$S_{24 \times 24} := 8664; \quad T_{576} := 24 \times 8664 = 207936 = 456^2;$$

$$S_{22 \times 22} := 7942; \quad T_{484} := 22 \times 7942 = 174724 = 418^2;$$

$$S_{20 \times 20} := 7220; \quad T_{400} := 20 \times 7220 = 144400 = 380^2;$$

$$S_{18 \times 18} := 6498; \quad T_{324} := 18 \times 6498 = 116964 = 342^2;$$

$$S_{16 \times 16} := 5776; \quad T_{256} := 16 \times 5776 = 92416 = 304^2;$$

$$S_{14 \times 14} := 5054; \quad T_{196} := 14 \times 5054 = 70756 = 266^2;$$

$$S_{12 \times 12} := 4332; \quad T_{144} := 12 \times 4332 = 51984 = 228^2;$$

$$S_{10 \times 10} := 3610; \quad T_{100} := 10 \times 3610 = 36100 = 190^2;$$

$$S_{8 \times 8} := 2888; \quad T_{64} := 8 \times 2888 = 23104 = 152^2;$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} := 2166; \quad T_{36} := 6 \times 2166 = 12996 = 114^2;$$

$$S_{4 \times 4} := 1444; \quad T_{16} := 4 \times 1444 = 5776 = 76^2;$$

$$T_4 := 1444 := 38^2.$$

19.2 Block-Wise Bordered Magic Square of Order 26

Example 33. A *block-wise bordered* magic square of order 26 for the *consecutive fraction entries* $\{47/2, 49/2, \dots, 1395/2, 1397/2\}$ is given by

47.5	685.5	37.5	683.5	39.5	681.5	41.5	679.5	43.5	677.5	45.5	675.5	23.5	686.5	49.5	671.5	51.5	669.5	53.5	667.5	55.5	665.5	57.5	663.5	59.5	673.5
61.5	80.5	74.5	646.5	648.5	635.5	85.5	637.5	79.5	112.5	106.5	614.5	616.5	603.5	117.5	605.5	111.5	144.5	138.5	582.5	584.5	571.5	149.5	573.5	143.5	660.5
659.5	77.5	630.5	628.5	89.5	634.5	90.5	92.5	644.5	109.5	598.5	596.5	121.5	602.5	122.5	124.5	612.5	141.5	566.5	564.5	153.5	570.5	154.5	156.5	580.5	62.5
63.5	78.5	88.5	622.5	97.5	100.5	623.5	633.5	643.5	110.5	120.5	590.5	129.5	132.5	591.5	601.5	611.5	142.5	152.5	558.5	161.5	164.5	559.5	569.5	579.5	658.5
657.5	83.5	94.5	103.5	620.5	617.5	102.5	627.5	638.5	115.5	126.5	135.5	588.5	585.5	134.5	595.5	606.5	147.5	158.5	167.5	556.5	553.5	166.5	563.5	574.5	64.5
65.5	645.5	96.5	619.5	104.5	101.5	618.5	625.5	76.5	613.5	128.5	587.5	136.5	133.5	586.5	593.5	108.5	581.5	160.5	555.5	168.5	165.5	554.5	561.5	140.5	656.5
655.5	640.5	626.5	98.5	621.5	624.5	99.5	95.5	81.5	608.5	594.5	130.5	589.5	592.5	131.5	127.5	113.5	576.5	562.5	162.5	557.5	560.5	163.5	159.5	145.5	66.5
67.5	639.5	629.5	93.5	632.5	87.5	631.5	91.5	82.5	607.5	597.5	125.5	600.5	119.5	599.5	123.5	114.5	575.5	565.5	157.5	568.5	151.5	567.5	155.5	146.5	654.5
653.5	642.5	647.5	75.5	73.5	86.5	636.5	84.5	641.5	610.5	615.5	107.5	105.5	118.5	604.5	116.5	609.5	578.5	583.5	139.5	137.5	150.5	572.5	148.5	577.5	68.5
69.5	176.5	170.5	550.5	552.5	539.5	181.5	541.5	175.5	208.5	202.5	518.5	520.5	507.5	213.5	509.5	207.5	240.5	234.5	486.5	488.5	475.5	245.5	477.5	239.5	652.5
651.5	173.5	534.5	532.5	185.5	538.5	186.5	188.5	548.5	205.5	502.5	500.5	217.5	506.5	218.5	220.5	516.5	237.5	470.5	468.5	249.5	474.5	250.5	252.5	484.5	70.5
71.5	174.5	184.5	526.5	193.5	196.5	527.5	537.5	547.5	206.5	216.5	494.5	225.5	228.5	495.5	505.5	515.5	238.5	248.5	462.5	257.5	260.5	463.5	473.5	483.5	650.5
649.5	179.5	190.5	199.5	524.5	521.5	198.5	531.5	542.5	211.5	222.5	231.5	492.5	489.5	230.5	499.5	510.5	243.5	254.5	263.5	460.5	457.5	262.5	467.5	478.5	72.5
661.5	549.5	192.5	523.5	200.5	197.5	522.5	529.5	172.5	517.5	224.5	491.5	232.5	229.5	490.5	497.5	204.5	485.5	256.5	459.5	264.5	261.5	458.5	465.5	236.5	60.5
687.5	544.5	530.5	194.5	525.5	528.5	195.5	191.5	177.5	512.5	498.5	226.5	493.5	496.5	227.5	223.5	209.5	480.5	466.5	258.5	461.5	464.5	259.5	255.5	241.5	34.5
33.5	543.5	533.5	189.5	536.5	183.5	535.5	187.5	178.5	511.5	501.5	221.5	504.5	215.5	503.5	219.5	210.5	479.5	469.5	253.5	472.5	247.5	471.5	251.5	242.5	688.5
689.5	546.5	551.5	171.5	169.5	182.5	540.5	180.5	545.5	514.5	519.5	203.5	201.5	214.5	508.5	212.5	513.5	482.5	487.5	235.5	233.5	246.5	476.5	244.5	481.5	32.5
31.5	272.5	266.5	454.5	456.5	443.5	277.5	445.5	271.5	304.5	298.5	422.5	424.5	411.5	309.5	413.5	303.5	336.5	330.5	390.5	392.5	379.5	341.5	381.5	335.5	690.5
691.5	269.5	438.5	436.5	281.5	442.5	282.5	284.5	452.5	301.5	406.5	404.5	313.5	410.5	314.5	316.5	420.5	333.5	374.5	372.5	345.5	378.5	346.5	348.5	388.5	30.5
29.5	270.5	280.5	430.5	289.5	292.5	431.5	441.5	451.5	302.5	312.5	398.5	321.5	324.5	399.5	409.5	419.5	334.5	344.5	366.5	353.5	356.5	367.5	377.5	387.5	692.5
693.5	275.5	286.5	295.5	428.5	425.5	294.5	435.5	446.5	307.5	318.5	327.5	396.5	393.5	326.5	403.5	414.5	339.5	350.5	359.5	364.5	361.5	358.5	371.5	382.5	28.5
27.5	453.5	288.5	427.5	296.5	293.5	426.5	433.5	268.5	421.5	320.5	395.5	328.5	325.5	394.5	401.5	300.5	389.5	352.5	363.5	360.5	357.5	362.5	369.5	332.5	694.5
695.5	448.5	434.5	290.5	429.5	432.5	291.5	287.5	273.5	416.5	402.5	322.5	397.5	400.5	323.5	319.5	305.5	384.5	370.5	354.5	365.5	368.5	355.5	351.5	337.5	26.5
25.5	447.5	437.5	285.5	440.5	279.5	439.5	283.5	274.5	415.5	405.5	317.5	408.5	311.5	407.5	315.5	306.5	383.5	373.5	349.5	376.5	343.5	375.5	347.5	338.5	696.5
697.5	450.5	455.5	267.5	265.5	278.5	444.5	276.5	449.5	418.5	423.5	299.5	297.5	310.5	412.5	308.5	417.5	386.5	391.5	331.5	329.5	342.5	380.5	340.5	385.5	24.5
48.5	36.5	684.5	38.5	682.5	40.5	680.5	42.5	678.5	44.5	676.5	46.5	698.5	35.5	672.5	50.5	670.5	52.5	668.5	54.5	666.5	56.5	664.5	58.5	662.5	674.5

Below are details of **magic** and **entries** sums of **block-wise bordered** magic square of order 26. The entries sum is **minimum perfect square**. It is formed by inner block of magic square of order 24 with 9 blocks of **bordered** magic squares of order 8 with equal magic sums.

$$S_{26 \times 26} := 9386; \quad T_{676} := 26 \times 9386 = 244036 = 494^2;$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} := 2166; \quad T_{36} := 6 \times 2166 = 12996 = 114^2;$$

$$S_{24 \times 24} := 8664; \quad T_{576} := 24 \times 8664 = 207936 = 456^2;$$

$$S_{4 \times 4} := 1444; \quad T_{16} := 4 \times 1444 = 5776 = 76^2;$$

$$S_{8 \times 8} := 2888; \quad T_{64} := 8 \times 2888 = 23104 = 152^2;$$

$$T_4 := 1444 := 38^2.$$

20 Bordered Magic Square of Order 27

This section brings **bordered** magic square of order 27 resulting in **minimum perfect square sum** of entries.

Example 34. A *bordered magic square* of order 27 for the *consecutive natural number entries* {36, 37, ..., 763, 764} is given by

739	713	715	717	719	721	723	725	727	729	731	733	735	60	59	57	55	53	51	49	47	45	43	41	39	37	737
86	689	665	667	669	671	673	675	677	679	681	683	685	110	109	107	105	103	101	99	97	95	93	91	89	687	714
84	134	643	621	623	625	627	629	631	633	635	637	639	156	155	153	151	149	147	145	143	141	139	137	641	666	716
82	132	178	601	581	583	585	587	589	591	593	595	597	198	197	195	193	191	189	187	185	183	181	599	622	668	718
80	130	176	218	563	545	547	549	551	553	555	557	559	236	235	233	231	229	227	225	223	221	561	582	624	670	720
78	128	174	216	254	529	513	515	517	519	521	523	525	270	269	267	265	263	261	259	257	527	546	584	626	672	722
76	126	172	214	252	286	499	485	487	489	491	493	495	300	299	297	295	293	291	289	497	514	548	586	628	674	724
74	124	170	212	250	284	314	473	461	463	465	467	469	326	325	323	321	319	317	471	486	516	550	588	630	676	726
72	122	168	210	248	282	312	338	451	441	443	445	447	348	347	345	343	341	449	462	488	518	552	590	632	678	728
70	120	166	208	246	280	310	336	358	433	425	427	429	366	365	363	361	431	442	464	490	520	554	592	634	680	730
68	118	164	206	244	278	308	334	356	374	419	413	415	380	379	377	417	426	444	466	492	522	556	594	636	682	732
66	116	162	204	242	276	306	332	354	372	386	409	405	390	389	407	414	428	446	468	494	524	558	596	638	684	734
64	114	160	202	240	274	304	330	352	370	384	394	403	396	401	406	416	430	448	470	496	526	560	598	640	686	736
62	112	158	200	238	272	302	328	350	368	382	392	398	400	402	408	418	432	450	472	498	528	562	600	642	688	738
742	692	646	604	566	532	502	476	454	436	422	412	399	404	397	388	378	364	346	324	298	268	234	196	154	108	58
744	694	648	606	568	534	504	478	456	438	424	393	395	410	411	391	376	362	344	322	296	266	232	194	152	106	56
746	696	650	608	570	536	506	480	458	440	383	387	385	420	421	423	381	360	342	320	294	264	230	192	150	104	54
748	698	652	610	572	538	508	482	460	369	375	373	371	434	435	437	439	367	340	318	292	262	228	190	148	102	52
750	700	654	612	574	540	510	484	351	359	357	355	353	452	453	455	457	459	349	316	290	260	226	188	146	100	50
752	702	656	614	576	542	512	329	339	337	335	333	331	474	475	477	479	481	483	327	288	258	224	186	144	98	48
754	704	658	616	578	544	303	315	313	311	309	307	305	500	501	503	505	507	509	511	301	256	222	184	142	96	46
756	706	660	618	580	273	287	285	283	281	279	277	275	530	531	533	535	537	539	541	543	271	220	182	140	94	44
758	708	662	620	239	255	253	251	249	247	245	243	241	564	565	567	569	571	573	575	577	579	237	180	138	92	42
760	710	664	201	219	217	215	213	211	209	207	205	203	602	603	605	607	609	611	613	615	617	619	199	136	90	40
762	712	159	179	177	175	173	171	169	167	165	163	161	644	645	647	649	651	653	655	657	659	661	663	157	88	38
764	113	135	133	131	129	127	125	123	121	119	117	115	690	691	693	695	697	699	701	703	705	707	709	711	111	36
63	87	85	83	81	79	77	75	73	71	69	67	65	740	741	743	745	747	749	751	753	755	757	759	761	763	61

Below are details of **magic** and **entries** sums of **bordered** magic square of order 27. The entries sum is **minimum perfect square**:

$$S_{27 \times 27} := 10800; \quad T_{729} := 27 \times 10800 = 291600 = 540^2;$$

$$S_{25 \times 25} := 10000; \quad T_{625} := 25 \times 10000 = 250000 = 500^2;$$

$$S_{23 \times 23} := 9200; \quad T_{529} := 23 \times 9200 = 211600 = 460^2;$$

$$S_{21 \times 21} := 8400; \quad T_{441} := 21 \times 8400 = 176400 = 420^2;$$

$$S_{19 \times 19} := 7600; \quad T_{361} := 19 \times 7600 = 144400 = 380^2;$$

$$S_{17 \times 17} := 6800; \quad T_{289} := 17 \times 6800 = 115600 = 340^2;$$

$$S_{15 \times 15} := 6000; \quad T_{225} := 15 \times 6000 = 90000 = 300^2;$$

$$S_{13 \times 13} := 5200; \quad T_{169} := 13 \times 5200 = 67600 = 260^2;$$

$$S_{11 \times 11} := 4400; \quad T_{121} := 11 \times 4400 = 48400 = 220^2;$$

$$S_{9 \times 9} := 3600; \quad T_{81} := 9 \times 3600 = 32400 = 180^2;$$

$$S_{7 \times 7} := 2800; \quad T_{49} := 7 \times 2800 = 19600 = 140^2;$$

$$S_{5 \times 5} := 2000; \quad T_{25} := 5 \times 2000 = 10000 = 100^2;$$

$$S_{3 \times 3} := 1200; \quad T_9 := 3 \times 1200 = 3600 = 60^2;$$

$$T_1 := 400 = 20^2.$$

21 Magic Squares of Order 28

This section brings **bordered** and **block-wise bordered** magic squares of orders 28 resulting in **minimum perfect square sum** of entries.

21.1 Bordered Magic Square of Order 28

Example 35. A bordered magic square of order 26 for the consecutive fraction entries $\{17/2, 19/2, \dots, 1581/2, 1583/2\}$ is given by

764.5	739.5	741.5	743.5	745.5	747.5	749.5	780.5	782.5	784.5	786.5	788.5	790.5	61.5	59.5	57.5	55.5	53.5	51.5	49.5	20.5	18.5	16.5	14.5	12.5	10.5	8.5	765.5
48.5	712.5	689.5	691.5	693.5	695.5	697.5	699.5	727.5	729.5	731.5	733.5	735.5	111.5	109.5	107.5	105.5	103.5	101.5	99.5	73.5	71.5	69.5	67.5	65.5	63.5	713.5	751.5
46.5	98.5	664.5	643.5	645.5	647.5	649.5	651.5	678.5	680.5	682.5	684.5	686.5	157.5	155.5	153.5	151.5	149.5	147.5	122.5	120.5	118.5	116.5	114.5	112.5	665.5	701.5	753.5
44.5	96.5	146.5	620.5	601.5	603.5	605.5	607.5	609.5	633.5	635.5	637.5	639.5	199.5	197.5	195.5	193.5	191.5	189.5	167.5	165.5	163.5	161.5	159.5	621.5	653.5	703.5	755.5
42.5	94.5	144.5	188.5	580.5	563.5	565.5	567.5	569.5	592.5	594.5	596.5	598.5	237.5	235.5	233.5	231.5	229.5	208.5	206.5	204.5	202.5	200.5	581.5	611.5	655.5	705.5	757.5
40.5	92.5	142.5	186.5	228.5	544.5	529.5	531.5	533.5	535.5	555.5	557.5	559.5	271.5	269.5	267.5	265.5	263.5	245.5	243.5	241.5	239.5	545.5	571.5	613.5	657.5	707.5	759.5
37.5	90.5	140.5	184.5	226.5	262.5	512.5	499.5	501.5	503.5	522.5	524.5	526.5	301.5	299.5	297.5	295.5	278.5	276.5	274.5	272.5	513.5	537.5	573.5	615.5	659.5	709.5	762.5
36.5	88.5	137.5	182.5	224.5	260.5	294.5	484.5	473.5	475.5	477.5	493.5	495.5	327.5	325.5	323.5	321.5	307.5	305.5	303.5	485.5	505.5	539.5	575.5	617.5	662.5	711.5	763.5
31.5	84.5	136.5	180.5	221.5	258.5	292.5	320.5	460.5	451.5	453.5	468.5	470.5	349.5	347.5	345.5	332.5	330.5	328.5	461.5	479.5	507.5	541.5	578.5	619.5	663.5	715.5	768.5
29.5	82.5	131.5	176.5	220.5	256.5	289.5	318.5	344.5	440.5	433.5	435.5	447.5	367.5	365.5	363.5	353.5	351.5	441.5	455.5	481.5	510.5	543.5	579.5	623.5	668.5	717.5	770.5
27.5	80.5	129.5	174.5	215.5	252.5	288.5	316.5	341.5	362.5	424.5	419.5	430.5	381.5	379.5	370.5	368.5	425.5	437.5	458.5	483.5	511.5	547.5	584.5	625.5	670.5	719.5	772.5
25.5	78.5	127.5	172.5	213.5	250.5	283.5	312.5	340.5	360.5	377.5	412.5	409.5	391.5	389.5	383.5	413.5	422.5	439.5	459.5	487.5	516.5	549.5	586.5	627.5	672.5	721.5	774.5
23.5	76.5	125.5	170.5	211.5	248.5	281.5	310.5	335.5	356.5	376.5	388.5	407.5	404.5	395.5	392.5	411.5	423.5	443.5	464.5	489.5	518.5	551.5	588.5	629.5	674.5	723.5	776.5
21.5	62.5	123.5	158.5	209.5	238.5	279.5	302.5	333.5	350.5	371.5	382.5	393.5	394.5	405.5	406.5	417.5	428.5	449.5	466.5	497.5	520.5	561.5	590.5	641.5	676.5	737.5	778.5
752.5	702.5	654.5	612.5	572.5	538.5	506.5	480.5	456.5	438.5	421.5	414.5	396.5	399.5	400.5	403.5	385.5	378.5	361.5	343.5	319.5	293.5	261.5	227.5	187.5	145.5	97.5	47.5
754.5	704.5	656.5	614.5	574.5	540.5	508.5	482.5	457.5	442.5	426.5	415.5	402.5	401.5	398.5	397.5	384.5	373.5	357.5	342.5	317.5	291.5	259.5	225.5	185.5	143.5	95.5	45.5
756.5	706.5	658.5	616.5	576.5	542.5	509.5	486.5	462.5	444.5	427.5	386.5	390.5	408.5	410.5	416.5	387.5	372.5	355.5	337.5	313.5	290.5	257.5	223.5	183.5	141.5	93.5	43.5
758.5	708.5	660.5	618.5	577.5	546.5	514.5	488.5	463.5	445.5	374.5	380.5	369.5	418.5	420.5	429.5	431.5	375.5	354.5	336.5	311.5	285.5	253.5	222.5	181.5	139.5	91.5	41.5
760.5	710.5	661.5	622.5	582.5	548.5	515.5	490.5	465.5	358.5	366.5	364.5	352.5	432.5	434.5	436.5	446.5	448.5	359.5	334.5	309.5	284.5	251.5	217.5	177.5	138.5	89.5	39.5
761.5	714.5	666.5	624.5	583.5	550.5	517.5	491.5	338.5	348.5	346.5	331.5	329.5	450.5	452.5	454.5	467.5	469.5	471.5	339.5	308.5	282.5	249.5	216.5	175.5	133.5	85.5	38.5
766.5	716.5	667.5	626.5	585.5	552.5	519.5	314.5	326.5	324.5	322.5	306.5	304.5	472.5	474.5	476.5	478.5	492.5	494.5	496.5	315.5	280.5	247.5	214.5	173.5	132.5	83.5	33.5
767.5	718.5	669.5	628.5	587.5	553.5	286.5	300.5	298.5	296.5	277.5	275.5	273.5	498.5	500.5	502.5	504.5	521.5	523.5	525.5	527.5	287.5	246.5	212.5	171.5	130.5	81.5	32.5
769.5	720.5	671.5	630.5	589.5	254.5	270.5	268.5	266.5	264.5	244.5	242.5	240.5	528.5	530.5	532.5	534.5	536.5	554.5	556.5	558.5	560.5	255.5	210.5	169.5	128.5	79.5	30.5
771.5	722.5	673.5	631.5	218.5	236.5	234.5	232.5	230.5	207.5	205.5	203.5	201.5	562.5	564.5	566.5	568.5	570.5	591.5	593.5	595.5	597.5	599.5	219.5	168.5	126.5	77.5	28.5
773.5	724.5	675.5	178.5	198.5	196.5	194.5	192.5	190.5	166.5	164.5	162.5	160.5	600.5	602.5	604.5	606.5	608.5	610.5	632.5	634.5	636.5	638.5	640.5	179.5	124.5	75.5	26.5
775.5	725.5	134.5	156.5	154.5	152.5	150.5	148.5	121.5	119.5	117.5	115.5	113.5	642.5	644.5	646.5	648.5	650.5	652.5	677.5	679.5	681.5	683.5	685.5	687.5	135.5	74.5	24.5
777.5	86.5	110.5	108.5	106.5	104.5	102.5	100.5	72.5	70.5	68.5	66.5	64.5	688.5	690.5	692.5	694.5	696.5	698.5	700.5	726.5	728.5	730.5	732.5	734.5	736.5	87.5	22.5
34.5	60.5	58.5	56.5	54.5	52.5	50.5	19.5	17.5	15.5	13.5	11.5	9.5	738.5	740.5	742.5	744.5	746.5	748.5	750.5	779.5	781.5	783.5	785.5	787.5	789.5	791.5	35.5

Below are details of **magic** and **entries** sums of **bordered** magic square of order 28. The entries sum is **minimum perfect square**:

$$S_{28 \times 28} := 11200; \quad T_{784} := 28 \times 11200 = 313600 = 560^2;$$

$$S_{26 \times 26} := 10400; \quad T_{676} := 26 \times 10400 = 270400 = 520^2;$$

$$S_{24 \times 24} := 9600; \quad T_{576} := 24 \times 9600 = 230400 = 480^2;$$

$$S_{22 \times 22} := 8800; \quad T_{484} := 22 \times 8800 = 193600 = 440^2;$$

$$S_{20 \times 20} := 8000; \quad T_{400} := 20 \times 8000 = 160000 = 400^2;$$

$$S_{18 \times 18} := 7200; \quad T_{324} := 18 \times 7200 = 129600 = 360^2;$$

$$S_{16 \times 16} := 6400; \quad T_{256} := 16 \times 6400 = 102400 = 320^2;$$

$$S_{14 \times 14} := 5600; \quad T_{196} := 14 \times 5600 = 78400 = 280^2;$$

$$S_{12 \times 12} := 4800; \quad T_{144} := 12 \times 4800 = 57600 = 240^2;$$

$$S_{10 \times 10} := 4000; \quad T_{100} := 10 \times 4000 = 40000 = 200^2;$$

$$S_{8 \times 8} := 3200; \quad T_{64} := 8 \times 3200 = 25600 = 160^2;$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} := 2400; \quad T_{36} := 6 \times 2400 = 14400 = 120^2;$$

$$S_{4 \times 4} := 1600; \quad T_{16} := 4 \times 1600 = 6400 = 80^2;$$

$$T_4 := 1600 := 40^2.$$

21.2 Block-Wise Bordered Magic Square of Order 28

Example 36. A *block-wise bordered* magic square of order 26 for the *consecutive fraction entries* $\{17/2, 19/2, \dots, 1581/2, 1583/2\}$ is given by

21.5	15.5	783.5	17.5	781.5	19.5	791.5	14.5	777.5	23.5	775.5	25.5	773.5	779.5	119.5	113.5	685.5	115.5	683.5	117.5	693.5	112.5	679.5	121.5	677.5	123.5	675.5	681.5
790.5	755.5	764.5	36.5	762.5	38.5	34.5	55.5	745.5	53.5	747.5	51.5	754.5	9.5	692.5	657.5	666.5	134.5	664.5	136.5	132.5	153.5	647.5	151.5	649.5	149.5	656.5	107.5
10.5	49.5	734.5	729.5	71.5	727.5	73.5	69.5	59.5	741.5	57.5	735.5	750.5	789.5	108.5	147.5	636.5	631.5	169.5	629.5	171.5	167.5	157.5	643.5	155.5	637.5	652.5	691.5
788.5	48.5	68.5	81.5	75.5	723.5	725.5	712.5	86.5	714.5	80.5	731.5	751.5	11.5	690.5	146.5	166.5	179.5	173.5	625.5	627.5	614.5	184.5	616.5	178.5	633.5	653.5	109.5
12.5	752.5	732.5	78.5	707.5	705.5	90.5	711.5	91.5	93.5	721.5	67.5	47.5	787.5	110.5	654.5	634.5	176.5	609.5	607.5	188.5	613.5	189.5	191.5	623.5	165.5	145.5	689.5
786.5	753.5	66.5	79.5	89.5	699.5	98.5	101.5	700.5	710.5	720.5	733.5	46.5	13.5	688.5	655.5	164.5	177.5	187.5	601.5	196.5	199.5	602.5	612.5	622.5	635.5	144.5	111.5
772.5	760.5	739.5	84.5	95.5	104.5	697.5	694.5	103.5	704.5	715.5	60.5	39.5	27.5	674.5	662.5	641.5	182.5	193.5	202.5	599.5	596.5	201.5	606.5	617.5	158.5	137.5	125.5
766.5	749.5	56.5	722.5	97.5	696.5	105.5	102.5	695.5	702.5	77.5	743.5	50.5	33.5	668.5	651.5	154.5	624.5	195.5	598.5	203.5	200.5	597.5	604.5	175.5	645.5	148.5	131.5
32.5	43.5	736.5	717.5	703.5	99.5	698.5	701.5	100.5	96.5	82.5	63.5	756.5	767.5	130.5	141.5	638.5	619.5	605.5	197.5	600.5	603.5	198.5	194.5	180.5	161.5	658.5	669.5
768.5	42.5	62.5	716.5	706.5	94.5	709.5	88.5	708.5	92.5	83.5	737.5	757.5	31.5	670.5	140.5	160.5	618.5	608.5	192.5	611.5	186.5	610.5	190.5	181.5	639.5	659.5	129.5
30.5	758.5	738.5	719.5	724.5	76.5	74.5	87.5	713.5	85.5	718.5	61.5	41.5	769.5	128.5	660.5	640.5	621.5	626.5	174.5	172.5	185.5	615.5	183.5	620.5	159.5	139.5	671.5
770.5	40.5	64.5	70.5	728.5	72.5	726.5	730.5	740.5	58.5	742.5	65.5	759.5	29.5	672.5	138.5	162.5	168.5	630.5	170.5	628.5	632.5	642.5	156.5	644.5	163.5	661.5	127.5
28.5	45.5	35.5	763.5	37.5	761.5	765.5	744.5	54.5	746.5	52.5	748.5	44.5	771.5	126.5	143.5	133.5	665.5	135.5	663.5	667.5	646.5	152.5	648.5	150.5	650.5	142.5	673.5
20.5	784.5	16.5	782.5	18.5	780.5	8.5	785.5	22.5	776.5	24.5	774.5	26.5	778.5	118.5	686.5	114.5	684.5	116.5	682.5	106.5	687.5	120.5	678.5	122.5	676.5	124.5	680.5
217.5	211.5	587.5	213.5	585.5	215.5	595.5	210.5	581.5	219.5	579.5	221.5	577.5	583.5	315.5	309.5	489.5	311.5	487.5	313.5	497.5	308.5	483.5	317.5	481.5	319.5	479.5	485.5
594.5	559.5	568.5	232.5	566.5	234.5	230.5	251.5	549.5	249.5	551.5	247.5	558.5	205.5	496.5	461.5	470.5	330.5	468.5	332.5	328.5	349.5	451.5	347.5	453.5	345.5	460.5	303.5
206.5	245.5	538.5	533.5	267.5	531.5	269.5	265.5	255.5	545.5	253.5	539.5	554.5	593.5	304.5	343.5	440.5	435.5	365.5	433.5	367.5	363.5	353.5	447.5	351.5	441.5	456.5	495.5
592.5	244.5	264.5	277.5	271.5	527.5	529.5	516.5	282.5	518.5	276.5	535.5	555.5	207.5	494.5	342.5	362.5	375.5	369.5	429.5	431.5	418.5	380.5	420.5	374.5	437.5	457.5	305.5
208.5	556.5	536.5	274.5	511.5	509.5	286.5	515.5	287.5	289.5	525.5	263.5	243.5	591.5	306.5	458.5	438.5	372.5	413.5	411.5	384.5	417.5	385.5	387.5	427.5	361.5	341.5	493.5
590.5	557.5	262.5	275.5	285.5	503.5	294.5	297.5	504.5	514.5	524.5	537.5	242.5	209.5	492.5	459.5	360.5	373.5	383.5	405.5	392.5	395.5	406.5	416.5	426.5	439.5	340.5	307.5
576.5	564.5	543.5	280.5	291.5	300.5	501.5	498.5	299.5	508.5	519.5	256.5	235.5	223.5	478.5	466.5	445.5	378.5	389.5	398.5	403.5	400.5	397.5	410.5	421.5	354.5	333.5	321.5
570.5	553.5	252.5	526.5	293.5	500.5	301.5	298.5	499.5	506.5	273.5	547.5	246.5	229.5	472.5	455.5	350.5	428.5	391.5	402.5	399.5	396.5	401.5	408.5	371.5	449.5	344.5	327.5
228.5	239.5	540.5	521.5	507.5	295.5	502.5	505.5	296.5	292.5	278.5	259.5	560.5	571.5	326.5	337.5	442.5	423.5	409.5	393.5	404.5	407.5	394.5	390.5	376.5	357.5	462.5	473.5
572.5	238.5	258.5	520.5	510.5	290.5	513.5	284.5	512.5	288.5	279.5	541.5	561.5	227.5	474.5	336.5	356.5	422.5	412.5	388.5	415.5	382.5	414.5	386.5	377.5	443.5	463.5	325.5
226.5	562.5	542.5	523.5	528.5	272.5	270.5	283.5	517.5	281.5	522.5	257.5	237.5	573.5	324.5	464.5	444.5	425.5	430.5	370.5	368.5	381.5	419.5	379.5	424.5	355.5	335.5	475.5
574.5	236.5	260.5	266.5	532.5	268.5	530.5	534.5	544.5	254.5	546.5	261.5	563.5	225.5	476.5	334.5	358.5	364.5	434.5	366.5	432.5	436.5	446.5	352.5	448.5	359.5	465.5	323.5
224.5	241.5	231.5	567.5	233.5	565.5	569.5	548.5	250.5	550.5	248.5	552.5	240.5	575.5	322.5	339.5	329.5	469.5	331.5	467.5	471.5	450.5	348.5	452.5	346.5	454.5	338.5	477.5
216.5	588.5	212.5	586.5	214.5	584.5	204.5	589.5	218.5	580.5	220.5	578.5	222.5	582.5	314.5	490.5	310.5	488.5	312.5	486.5	302.5	491.5	316.5	482.5	318.5	480.5	320.5	484.5

Below are details of **magic** and **entries** sums of **block-wise bordered** magic square of order 28. The entries sum is **minimum perfect square**. It is formed by 4 blocks of **bordered** magic squares of order 14 with equal magic sums.

$$\begin{array}{ll}
 \mathbf{S}_{28 \times 28} := 11200; & \mathbf{T}_{784} := 28 \times 11200 = 313600 = 560^2; \\
 \mathbf{S}_{14 \times 14} := 5600; & \mathbf{T}_{196} := 14 \times 5600 = 78400 = 280^2; \\
 \mathbf{S}_{12 \times 12} := 4800; & \mathbf{T}_{144} := 12 \times 4800 = 57600 = 240^2; \\
 \mathbf{S}_{10 \times 10} := 4000; & \mathbf{T}_{100} := 10 \times 4000 = 40000 = 200^2; \\
 \mathbf{S}_{8 \times 8} := 3200; & \mathbf{T}_{64} := 8 \times 3200 = 25600 = 160^2; \\
 \mathbf{S}_{6 \times 6} := 2400; & \mathbf{T}_{36} := 6 \times 2400 = 14400 = 120^2; \\
 \mathbf{S}_{4 \times 4} := 1600; & \mathbf{T}_{16} := 4 \times 1600 = 6400 = 80^2; \\
 & \mathbf{T}_4 := 1600 = 40^2.
 \end{array}$$

22 Bordered Magic Square of Order 29

This section brings **bordered** magic square of order 29 resulting in **minimum perfect square sum** of entries.

Example 37. A *bordered magic square* of order 29 for the *consecutive natural number entries* {21, 22, ..., 860, 861} is given by

834	806	808	810	812	814	816	818	820	822	824	826	828	830	47	46	44	42	40	38	36	34	32	30	28	26	24	22	832
75	780	127	125	123	121	119	117	115	113	111	109	107	105	103	783	785	787	789	791	793	795	797	799	801	803	805	104	807
73	754	730	706	708	710	712	714	716	718	720	722	724	726	151	150	148	146	144	142	140	138	136	134	132	130	728	128	809
71	756	175	200	220	218	216	214	212	210	208	206	204	202	685	686	688	690	692	694	696	698	700	702	704	198	707	126	811
69	758	173	705	640	222	224	226	228	230	232	234	236	238	239	638	636	634	632	630	628	626	624	622	642	177	709	124	813
67	760	171	703	623	604	586	588	590	592	594	596	598	600	277	276	274	272	270	268	266	264	262	602	259	179	711	122	815
65	762	169	701	625	295	312	584	582	580	578	576	574	572	571	316	318	320	322	324	326	328	314	587	257	181	713	120	817
63	764	167	699	627	293	297	342	552	550	548	546	544	542	541	346	348	350	352	354	356	344	585	589	255	183	715	118	819
61	766	165	697	629	291	299	329	370	380	378	376	374	372	515	516	518	520	522	524	368	553	583	591	253	185	717	116	821
59	768	163	695	631	289	301	331	525	492	399	397	395	393	391	495	497	499	501	392	357	551	581	593	251	187	719	114	823
57	770	161	693	633	287	303	333	523	482	472	402	404	406	407	470	468	466	474	400	359	549	579	595	249	189	721	112	825
55	772	159	691	635	285	305	335	521	484	467	424	428	426	461	462	464	422	415	398	361	547	577	597	247	191	723	110	827
53	774	157	689	637	283	307	337	519	486	469	465	448	447	449	429	432	417	413	396	363	545	575	599	245	193	725	108	829
51	776	155	687	639	281	309	339	517	488	471	463	430	442	437	444	452	419	411	394	365	543	573	601	243	195	727	106	831
49	101	153	199	641	279	569	539	369	389	473	423	431	443	441	439	451	459	409	493	513	343	313	603	241	683	729	781	833
837	100	733	201	237	607	567	537	371	388	405	425	446	438	445	440	436	457	477	494	511	345	315	275	645	681	149	782	45
839	98	735	203	235	609	565	535	373	386	403	427	450	435	433	453	434	455	479	496	509	347	317	273	647	679	147	784	43
841	96	737	205	233	611	563	533	375	384	401	460	454	456	421	420	418	458	481	498	507	349	319	271	649	677	145	786	41
843	94	739	207	231	613	561	531	377	382	408	480	478	476	475	412	414	416	410	500	505	351	321	269	651	675	143	788	39
845	92	741	209	229	615	559	529	379	490	483	485	487	489	491	387	385	383	381	390	503	353	323	267	653	673	141	790	37
847	90	743	211	227	617	557	527	514	502	504	506	508	510	367	366	364	362	360	358	512	355	325	265	655	671	139	792	35
849	88	745	213	225	619	555	538	330	332	334	336	338	340	341	536	534	532	530	528	526	540	327	263	657	669	137	794	33
851	86	747	215	223	621	568	298	300	302	304	306	308	310	311	566	564	562	560	558	556	554	570	261	659	667	135	796	31
853	84	749	217	221	280	296	294	292	290	288	286	284	282	605	606	608	610	612	614	616	618	620	278	661	665	133	798	29
855	82	751	219	240	660	658	656	654	652	650	648	646	644	643	244	246	248	250	252	254	256	258	260	242	663	131	800	27
857	80	753	684	662	664	666	668	670	672	674	676	678	680	197	196	194	192	190	188	186	184	182	180	178	682	129	802	25
859	78	154	176	174	172	170	168	166	164	162	160	158	156	731	732	734	736	738	740	742	744	746	748	750	752	152	804	23
861	778	755	757	759	761	763	765	767	769	771	773	775	777	779	99	97	95	93	91	89	87	85	83	81	79	77	102	21
50	76	74	72	70	68	66	64	62	60	58	56	54	52	835	836	838	840	842	844	846	848	850	852	854	856	858	860	48

Below are details of **magic** and **entries** sums of **bordered** magic square of order 29. The entries sum is **minimum perfect square**:

$$\begin{array}{ll} \mathbf{S}_{29 \times 29} := 12789; & \mathbf{T}_{841} := 29 \times 12789 \times 370881 = 609^2; \\ \mathbf{S}_{27 \times 27} := 11907; & \mathbf{T}_{729} := 27 \times 11907 \times 321489 = 567^2; \\ \mathbf{S}_{25 \times 25} := 11025; & \mathbf{T}_{625} := 25 \times 11025 \times 275625 = 525^2; \\ \mathbf{S}_{23 \times 23} := 10143; & \mathbf{T}_{529} := 23 \times 10143 \times 233289 = 483^2; \\ \mathbf{S}_{21 \times 21} := 9261; & \mathbf{T}_{441} := 21 \times 9261 \times 194481 = 441^2; \\ \mathbf{S}_{19 \times 19} := 8379; & \mathbf{T}_{361} := 19 \times 8379 \times 159201 = 399^2; \\ \mathbf{S}_{17 \times 17} := 7497; & \mathbf{T}_{289} := 17 \times 7497 \times 127449 = 357^2; \\ & \mathbf{S}_{15 \times 15} := 6615; & \mathbf{T}_{225} := 15 \times 6615 \times 99225 = 315^2; \\ & \mathbf{S}_{13 \times 13} := 5733; & \mathbf{T}_{169} := 13 \times 5733 \times 74529 = 273^2; \\ & \mathbf{S}_{11 \times 11} := 4851; & \mathbf{T}_{121} := 11 \times 4851 \times 53361 = 231^2; \\ & \mathbf{S}_{9 \times 9} := 3969; & \mathbf{T}_{81} := 9 \times 3969 \times 35721 = 189^2; \\ & \mathbf{S}_{7 \times 7} := 3087; & \mathbf{T}_{49} := 7 \times 3087 \times 21609 = 147^2; \\ & \mathbf{S}_{5 \times 5} := 2205; & \mathbf{T}_{25} := 5 \times 2205 \times 11025 = 105^2; \\ & \mathbf{S}_{3 \times 3} := 1323; & \mathbf{T}_9 := 3 \times 1323 \times 3969 = 63^2; \\ & & \mathbf{T}_1 := 441 = 21^2. \end{array}$$

23 Magic Squares of Order 30

This section brings **bordered** and **block-wise bordered** magic squares of orders 30 resulting in **minimum perfect square sum** of entries.

23.1 Bordered Magic Square of Order 30

Example 38. A bordered magic square of order 30 for the consecutive fraction entries $\{69/2, 71/2, \dots, 1865/2, 1867/2\}$ is given by

904.5	877.5	879.5	881.5	883.5	885.5	887.5	889.5	921.5	923.5	925.5	927.5	929.5	931.5	91.5	89.5	87.5	85.5	83.5	81.5	79.5	77.5	47.5	45.5	43.5	41.5	39.5	37.5	35.5	905.5
76.5	848.5	823.5	825.5	827.5	829.5	831.5	833.5	864.5	866.5	868.5	870.5	872.5	874.5	145.5	143.5	141.5	139.5	137.5	135.5	133.5	104.5	102.5	100.5	98.5	96.5	94.5	92.5	849.5	891.5
74.5	132.5	796.5	773.5	775.5	777.5	779.5	781.5	783.5	811.5	813.5	815.5	817.5	819.5	195.5	193.5	191.5	189.5	187.5	185.5	183.5	157.5	155.5	153.5	151.5	149.5	147.5	797.5	835.5	893.5
72.5	130.5	182.5	748.5	727.5	729.5	731.5	733.5	735.5	762.5	764.5	766.5	768.5	770.5	241.5	239.5	237.5	235.5	233.5	231.5	206.5	204.5	202.5	200.5	198.5	196.5	749.5	785.5	837.5	895.5
70.5	128.5	180.5	230.5	704.5	685.5	687.5	689.5	691.5	693.5	717.5	719.5	721.5	723.5	283.5	281.5	279.5	277.5	275.5	273.5	251.5	249.5	247.5	245.5	243.5	705.5	737.5	787.5	839.5	897.5
68.5	126.5	178.5	228.5	272.5	664.5	647.5	649.5	651.5	653.5	676.5	678.5	680.5	682.5	321.5	319.5	317.5	315.5	313.5	292.5	290.5	288.5	286.5	284.5	665.5	695.5	739.5	789.5	841.5	899.5
66.5	124.5	176.5	226.5	270.5	312.5	628.5	613.5	615.5	617.5	619.5	639.5	641.5	643.5	355.5	353.5	351.5	349.5	347.5	329.5	327.5	325.5	323.5	629.5	655.5	697.5	741.5	791.5	843.5	901.5
64.5	121.5	174.5	224.5	268.5	310.5	346.5	596.5	583.5	585.5	587.5	606.5	608.5	610.5	385.5	383.5	381.5	379.5	362.5	360.5	358.5	356.5	597.5	621.5	657.5	699.5	743.5	793.5	846.5	903.5
60.5	120.5	172.5	221.5	266.5	308.5	344.5	378.5	568.5	557.5	559.5	561.5	577.5	579.5	411.5	409.5	407.5	405.5	391.5	389.5	387.5	569.5	589.5	623.5	659.5	701.5	746.5	795.5	847.5	907.5
58.5	115.5	168.5	220.5	264.5	305.5	342.5	376.5	404.5	544.5	535.5	537.5	552.5	554.5	433.5	431.5	429.5	416.5	414.5	412.5	545.5	563.5	591.5	625.5	662.5	703.5	747.5	799.5	852.5	909.5
56.5	113.5	166.5	215.5	260.5	304.5	340.5	373.5	402.5	428.5	524.5	517.5	519.5	531.5	451.5	449.5	447.5	437.5	435.5	525.5	539.5	565.5	594.5	627.5	663.5	707.5	752.5	801.5	854.5	911.5
54.5	111.5	164.5	213.5	258.5	299.5	336.5	372.5	400.5	425.5	446.5	508.5	503.5	514.5	465.5	463.5	454.5	452.5	509.5	521.5	542.5	567.5	595.5	631.5	668.5	709.5	754.5	803.5	856.5	913.5
52.5	109.5	162.5	211.5	256.5	297.5	334.5	367.5	396.5	424.5	444.5	461.5	496.5	493.5	475.5	473.5	467.5	497.5	506.5	523.5	543.5	571.5	600.5	633.5	670.5	711.5	756.5	805.5	858.5	915.5
50.5	107.5	160.5	209.5	254.5	295.5	332.5	365.5	394.5	419.5	440.5	460.5	472.5	491.5	488.5	479.5	476.5	495.5	507.5	527.5	548.5	573.5	602.5	635.5	672.5	713.5	758.5	807.5	860.5	917.5
34.5	105.5	146.5	207.5	242.5	293.5	322.5	363.5	386.5	417.5	434.5	455.5	466.5	477.5	478.5	489.5	490.5	501.5	512.5	533.5	550.5	581.5	604.5	645.5	674.5	725.5	760.5	821.5	862.5	933.5
892.5	836.5	786.5	738.5	696.5	656.5	622.5	590.5	564.5	540.5	522.5	505.5	498.5	480.5	483.5	484.5	487.5	469.5	462.5	445.5	427.5	403.5	377.5	345.5	311.5	271.5	229.5	181.5	131.5	75.5
894.5	838.5	788.5	740.5	698.5	658.5	624.5	592.5	566.5	541.5	526.5	510.5	499.5	486.5	485.5	482.5	481.5	468.5	457.5	441.5	426.5	401.5	375.5	343.5	309.5	269.5	227.5	179.5	129.5	73.5
896.5	840.5	790.5	742.5	700.5	660.5	626.5	593.5	570.5	546.5	528.5	511.5	470.5	474.5	492.5	494.5	500.5	471.5	456.5	439.5	421.5	397.5	374.5	341.5	307.5	267.5	225.5	177.5	127.5	71.5
898.5	842.5	792.5	744.5	702.5	661.5	630.5	598.5	572.5	547.5	529.5	458.5	464.5	453.5	502.5	504.5	513.5	515.5	459.5	438.5	420.5	395.5	369.5	337.5	306.5	265.5	223.5	175.5	125.5	69.5
900.5	844.5	794.5	745.5	706.5	666.5	632.5	599.5	574.5	549.5	442.5	450.5	448.5	436.5	516.5	518.5	520.5	530.5	532.5	443.5	418.5	393.5	368.5	335.5	301.5	261.5	222.5	173.5	123.5	67.5
902.5	845.5	798.5	750.5	708.5	667.5	634.5	601.5	575.5	422.5	432.5	430.5	415.5	413.5	534.5	536.5	538.5	551.5	553.5	555.5	423.5	392.5	366.5	333.5	300.5	259.5	217.5	169.5	122.5	65.5
906.5	850.5	800.5	751.5	710.5	669.5	636.5	603.5	398.5	410.5	408.5	406.5	390.5	388.5	556.5	558.5	560.5	562.5	576.5	578.5	580.5	399.5	364.5	331.5	298.5	257.5	216.5	167.5	117.5	61.5
908.5	851.5	802.5	753.5	712.5	671.5	637.5	370.5	384.5	382.5	380.5	361.5	359.5	357.5	582.5	584.5	586.5	588.5	605.5	607.5	609.5	611.5	371.5	330.5	296.5	255.5	214.5	165.5	116.5	59.5
910.5	853.5	804.5	755.5	714.5	673.5	338.5	354.5	352.5	350.5	348.5	328.5	326.5	324.5	612.5	614.5	616.5	618.5	620.5	638.5	640.5	642.5	644.5	339.5	294.5	253.5	212.5	163.5	114.5	57.5
912.5	855.5	806.5	757.5	715.5	302.5	320.5	318.5	316.5	314.5	291.5	289.5	287.5	285.5	646.5	648.5	650.5	652.5	654.5	675.5	677.5	679.5	681.5	683.5	303.5	252.5	210.5	161.5	112.5	55.5
914.5	857.5	808.5	759.5	262.5	282.5	280.5	278.5	276.5	274.5	250.5	248.5	246.5	244.5	684.5	686.5	688.5	690.5	692.5	694.5	716.5	718.5	720.5	722.5	724.5	263.5	208.5	159.5	110.5	53.5
916.5	859.5	809.5	218.5	240.5	238.5	236.5	234.5	232.5	205.5	203.5	201.5	199.5	197.5	726.5	728.5	730.5	732.5	734.5	736.5	761.5	763.5	765.5	767.5	769.5	771.5	219.5	158.5	108.5	51.5
918.5	861.5	170.5	194.5	192.5	190.5	188.5	186.5	184.5	156.5	154.5	152.5	150.5	148.5	772.5	774.5	776.5	778.5	780.5	782.5	784.5	810.5	812.5	814.5	816.5	818.5	820.5	171.5	106.5	49.5
919.5	118.5	144.5	142.5	140.5	138.5	136.5	134.5	103.5	101.5	99.5	97.5	95.5	93.5	822.5	824.5	826.5	828.5	830.5	832.5	834.5	863.5	865.5	867.5	869.5	871.5	873.5	875.5	119.5	48.5
62.5	90.5	88.5	86.5	84.5	82.5	80.5	78.5	46.5	44.5	42.5	40.5	38.5	36.5	876.5	878.5	880.5	882.5	884.5	886.5	888.5	890.5	920.5	922.5	924.5	926.5	928.5	930.5	932.5	63.5

Below are details of **magic** and **entries** sums of **bordered** magic square of order 30. The entries sum is **minimum perfect square**:

$$S_{30 \times 30} := 14520; \quad T_{900} := 30 \times 14520 = 435600 = 660^2;$$

$$S_{28 \times 28} := 13552; \quad T_{784} := 28 \times 13552 = 379456 = 616^2;$$

$$S_{26 \times 26} := 12584; \quad T_{676} := 26 \times 12584 = 327184 = 572^2;$$

$$S_{24 \times 24} := 11616; \quad T_{576} := 24 \times 11616 = 278784 = 528^2;$$

$$S_{22 \times 22} := 10648; \quad T_{484} := 22 \times 10648 = 234256 = 484^2;$$

$$S_{20 \times 20} := 9680; \quad T_{400} := 20 \times 9680 = 193600 = 440^2;$$

$$S_{18 \times 18} := 8712; \quad T_{324} := 18 \times 8712 = 156816 = 396^2;$$

$$S_{16 \times 16} := 7744; \quad T_{256} := 16 \times 7744 = 123904 = 352^2;$$

$$S_{14 \times 14} := 6776; \quad T_{196} := 14 \times 6776 = 94864 = 308^2;$$

$$S_{12 \times 12} := 5808; \quad T_{144} := 12 \times 5808 = 69696 = 264^2;$$

$$S_{10 \times 10} := 4840; \quad T_{100} := 10 \times 4840 = 48400 = 220^2;$$

$$S_{8 \times 8} := 3872; \quad T_{64} := 8 \times 3872 = 30976 = 176^2;$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} := 2904; \quad T_{36} := 6 \times 2904 = 17424 = 132^2;$$

$$S_{4 \times 4} := 1936; \quad T_{16} := 4 \times 1936 = 7744 = 88^2;$$

$$T_4 := 1936 := 44^2.$$

23.2 Block-Wise Bordered Magic Square of Order 30

Example 39. A *block-wise bordered* magic square of order 30 for the *consecutive fraction entries* $\{69/2, 71/2, \dots, 1865/2, 1867/2\}$ is given by

924.5	919.5	49.5	917.5	51.5	47.5	37.5	931.5	35.5	925.5	874.5	869.5	99.5	867.5	101.5	97.5	87.5	881.5	85.5	875.5	824.5	819.5	149.5	817.5	151.5	147.5	137.5	831.5	135.5	825.5
46.5	59.5	53.5	913.5	915.5	902.5	64.5	904.5	58.5	921.5	96.5	109.5	103.5	863.5	865.5	852.5	114.5	854.5	108.5	871.5	146.5	159.5	153.5	813.5	815.5	802.5	164.5	804.5	158.5	821.5
922.5	56.5	897.5	895.5	68.5	901.5	69.5	71.5	911.5	45.5	872.5	106.5	847.5	845.5	118.5	851.5	119.5	121.5	861.5	95.5	822.5	156.5	797.5	795.5	168.5	801.5	169.5	171.5	811.5	145.5
44.5	57.5	67.5	889.5	76.5	79.5	890.5	900.5	910.5	923.5	94.5	107.5	117.5	839.5	126.5	129.5	840.5	850.5	860.5	873.5	144.5	157.5	167.5	789.5	176.5	179.5	790.5	800.5	810.5	823.5
929.5	62.5	73.5	82.5	887.5	884.5	81.5	894.5	905.5	38.5	879.5	112.5	123.5	132.5	837.5	834.5	131.5	844.5	855.5	88.5	829.5	162.5	173.5	182.5	787.5	784.5	181.5	794.5	805.5	138.5
34.5	912.5	75.5	886.5	83.5	80.5	885.5	892.5	55.5	933.5	84.5	862.5	125.5	836.5	133.5	130.5	835.5	842.5	105.5	883.5	134.5	812.5	175.5	786.5	183.5	180.5	785.5	792.5	155.5	833.5
926.5	907.5	893.5	77.5	888.5	891.5	78.5	74.5	60.5	41.5	876.5	857.5	843.5	127.5	838.5	841.5	128.5	124.5	110.5	91.5	826.5	807.5	793.5	177.5	788.5	791.5	178.5	174.5	160.5	141.5
40.5	906.5	896.5	72.5	899.5	66.5	898.5	70.5	61.5	927.5	90.5	856.5	846.5	122.5	849.5	116.5	848.5	120.5	111.5	877.5	140.5	806.5	796.5	172.5	799.5	166.5	798.5	170.5	161.5	827.5
928.5	909.5	914.5	54.5	52.5	65.5	903.5	63.5	908.5	39.5	878.5	859.5	864.5	104.5	102.5	115.5	853.5	113.5	858.5	89.5	828.5	809.5	814.5	154.5	152.5	165.5	803.5	163.5	808.5	139.5
42.5	48.5	918.5	50.5	916.5	920.5	930.5	36.5	932.5	43.5	92.5	98.5	868.5	100.5	866.5	870.5	880.5	86.5	882.5	93.5	142.5	148.5	818.5	150.5	816.5	820.5	830.5	136.5	832.5	143.5
774.5	769.5	199.5	767.5	201.5	197.5	187.5	781.5	185.5	775.5	724.5	719.5	249.5	717.5	251.5	247.5	237.5	731.5	235.5	725.5	674.5	669.5	299.5	667.5	301.5	297.5	287.5	681.5	285.5	675.5
196.5	209.5	203.5	763.5	765.5	752.5	214.5	754.5	208.5	771.5	246.5	259.5	253.5	713.5	715.5	702.5	264.5	704.5	258.5	721.5	296.5	309.5	303.5	663.5	665.5	652.5	314.5	654.5	308.5	671.5
772.5	206.5	747.5	745.5	218.5	751.5	219.5	221.5	761.5	195.5	722.5	256.5	697.5	695.5	268.5	701.5	269.5	271.5	711.5	245.5	672.5	306.5	647.5	645.5	318.5	651.5	319.5	321.5	661.5	295.5
194.5	207.5	217.5	739.5	226.5	229.5	740.5	750.5	760.5	773.5	244.5	257.5	267.5	689.5	276.5	279.5	690.5	700.5	710.5	723.5	294.5	307.5	317.5	639.5	326.5	329.5	640.5	650.5	660.5	673.5
779.5	212.5	223.5	232.5	737.5	734.5	231.5	744.5	755.5	188.5	729.5	262.5	273.5	282.5	687.5	684.5	281.5	694.5	705.5	238.5	679.5	312.5	323.5	332.5	637.5	634.5	331.5	644.5	655.5	288.5
184.5	762.5	225.5	736.5	233.5	230.5	735.5	742.5	205.5	783.5	234.5	712.5	275.5	686.5	283.5	280.5	685.5	692.5	255.5	733.5	284.5	662.5	325.5	636.5	333.5	330.5	635.5	642.5	305.5	683.5
776.5	757.5	743.5	227.5	738.5	741.5	228.5	224.5	210.5	191.5	726.5	707.5	693.5	277.5	688.5	691.5	278.5	274.5	260.5	241.5	676.5	657.5	643.5	327.5	638.5	641.5	328.5	324.5	310.5	291.5
190.5	756.5	746.5	222.5	749.5	216.5	748.5	220.5	211.5	777.5	240.5	706.5	696.5	272.5	699.5	266.5	698.5	270.5	261.5	727.5	290.5	656.5	646.5	322.5	649.5	316.5	648.5	320.5	311.5	677.5
778.5	759.5	764.5	204.5	202.5	215.5	753.5	213.5	758.5	189.5	728.5	709.5	714.5	254.5	252.5	265.5	703.5	263.5	708.5	239.5	678.5	659.5	664.5	304.5	302.5	315.5	653.5	313.5	658.5	289.5
192.5	198.5	768.5	200.5	766.5	770.5	780.5	186.5	782.5	193.5	242.5	248.5	718.5	250.5	716.5	720.5	730.5	236.5	732.5	243.5	292.5	298.5	668.5	300.5	666.5	670.5	680.5	286.5	682.5	293.5
624.5	619.5	349.5	617.5	351.5	347.5	337.5	631.5	335.5	625.5	574.5	569.5	399.5	567.5	401.5	397.5	387.5	581.5	385.5	575.5	524.5	519.5	449.5	517.5	451.5	447.5	437.5	531.5	435.5	525.5
346.5	359.5	353.5	613.5	615.5	602.5	364.5	604.5	358.5	621.5	396.5	409.5	403.5	563.5	565.5	552.5	414.5	554.5	408.5	571.5	446.5	459.5	453.5	513.5	515.5	502.5	464.5	504.5	458.5	521.5
622.5	356.5	597.5	595.5	368.5	601.5	369.5	371.5	611.5	345.5	572.5	406.5	547.5	545.5	418.5	551.5	419.5	421.5	561.5	395.5	522.5	456.5	497.5	495.5	468.5	501.5	469.5	471.5	511.5	445.5
344.5	357.5	367.5	589.5	376.5	379.5	590.5	600.5	610.5	623.5	394.5	407.5	417.5	539.5	426.5	429.5	540.5	550.5	560.5	573.5	444.5	457.5	467.5	489.5	476.5	479.5	490.5	500.5	510.5	523.5
629.5	362.5	373.5	382.5	587.5	584.5	381.5	594.5	605.5	338.5	579.5	412.5	423.5	432.5	537.5	534.5	431.5	544.5	555.5	388.5	529.5	462.5	473.5	482.5	487.5	484.5	481.5	494.5	505.5	438.5
334.5	612.5	375.5	586.5	383.5	380.5	585.5	592.5	355.5	633.5	384.5	562.5	425.5	536.5	433.5	430.5	535.5	542.5	405.5	583.5	434.5	512.5	475.5	486.5	483.5	480.5	485.5	492.5	455.5	533.5
626.5	607.5	593.5	377.5	588.5	591.5	378.5	374.5	360.5	341.5	576.5	557.5	543.5	427.5	538.5	541.5	428.5	424.5	410.5	391.5	526.5	507.5	493.5	477.5	488.5	491.5	478.5	474.5	460.5	441.5
340.5	606.5	596.5	372.5	599.5	366.5	598.5	370.5	361.5	627.5	390.5	556.5	546.5	422.5	549.5	416.5	548.5	420.5	411.5	577.5	440.5	506.5	496.5	472.5	499.5	466.5	498.5	470.5	461.5	527.5
628.5	609.5	614.5	354.5	352.5	365.5	603.5	363.5	608.5	339.5	578.5	559.5	564.5	404.5	402.5	415.5	553.5	413.5	558.5	389.5	528.5	509.5	514.5	454.5	452.5	465.5	503.5	463.5	508.5	439.5
342.5	348.5	618.5	350.5	616.5	620.5	630.5	336.5	632.5	343.5	392.5	398.5	568.5	400.5	566.5	570.5	580.5	386.5	582.5	393.5	442.5	448.5	518.5	450.5	516.5	520.5	530.5	436.5	532.5	443.5

Below are details of **magic** and **entries** sums of **block-wise bordered** magic square of order 30. The entries sum is **minimum perfect square**. It is formed by 9 blocks of **bordered** magic squares of order 10 with equal magic sums.

$$S_{30 \times 30} := 14520; \quad T_{900} := 30 \times 14520 = 435600 = 660^2;$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} := 2904; \quad T_{36} := 6 \times 2904 = 17424 = 132^2;$$

$$S_{10 \times 10} := 4840; \quad T_{100} := 10 \times 4840 = 48400 = 220^2;$$

$$S_{4 \times 4} := 1936; \quad T_{16} := 4 \times 1936 = 7744 = 88^2;$$

$$S_{8 \times 8} := 3872; \quad T_{64} := 8 \times 3872 = 30976 = 176^2;$$

$$T_4 := 1936 := 44^2.$$

24 Bordered Magic Square of Order 31

This section brings **bordered** magic square of order 31 resulting in **minimum perfect square sum** of entries.

Example 40. A *bordered magic square of order 31 for the consecutive natural number entries* $\{4, 5, \dots, 963, 964\}$ is given by

935	905	907	909	911	913	915	917	919	921	923	925	927	929	931	32	31	29	27	25	23	21	19	17	15	13	11	9	7	5	933
62	91	64	66	68	70	72	74	76	78	80	82	84	86	88	876	874	872	870	868	866	864	862	860	858	856	854	852	850	875	906
60	903	823	797	799	801	803	805	807	809	811	813	815	817	819	144	143	141	139	137	135	133	131	129	127	125	123	121	821	65	908
58	901	170	771	750	752	754	756	758	760	762	764	766	768	770	772	192	190	188	186	184	182	180	178	176	174	172	195	798	67	910
56	899	168	173	241	747	745	743	741	739	737	735	733	731	729	728	245	247	249	251	253	255	257	259	261	263	243	795	800	69	912
54	897	166	175	220	283	703	701	699	697	695	693	691	689	687	686	287	289	291	293	295	297	299	301	303	285	748	793	802	71	914
52	895	164	177	222	264	645	630	632	634	636	638	640	642	644	646	318	316	314	312	310	308	306	304	321	704	746	791	804	73	916
50	893	162	179	224	266	305	357	371	369	367	365	363	361	359	614	615	617	619	621	623	625	627	355	663	702	744	789	806	75	918
48	891	160	181	226	268	307	628	387	596	594	592	590	588	586	386	388	390	392	394	396	398	583	340	661	700	742	787	808	77	920
46	889	158	183	228	270	309	626	399	413	568	566	564	562	560	412	414	416	418	420	422	557	569	342	659	698	740	785	810	79	922
44	887	156	185	230	272	311	624	397	423	535	442	440	438	436	434	538	540	542	544	435	545	571	344	657	696	738	783	812	81	924
42	885	154	187	232	274	313	622	395	421	525	451	523	521	519	518	455	457	459	453	443	547	573	346	655	694	736	781	814	83	926
40	883	152	189	234	276	315	620	393	419	527	444	467	471	469	504	505	507	465	524	441	549	575	348	653	692	734	779	816	85	928
38	881	150	191	236	278	317	618	391	417	529	446	508	475	495	494	479	477	460	522	439	551	577	350	651	690	732	777	818	87	930
36	879	148	193	238	280	319	616	389	415	531	448	506	472	483	488	481	496	462	520	437	553	579	352	649	688	730	775	820	89	932
34	878	146	194	726	684	320	356	584	558	432	516	466	492	482	484	486	476	502	452	536	410	384	612	648	284	242	774	822	90	934
938	95	826	769	724	682	643	358	585	559	431	514	468	490	487	480	485	478	500	454	537	409	383	610	325	286	244	199	142	873	30
940	97	828	767	722	680	641	360	587	561	429	512	470	491	473	474	489	493	498	456	539	407	381	608	327	288	246	201	140	871	28
942	99	830	765	720	678	639	362	589	563	427	510	503	497	499	464	463	461	501	458	541	405	379	606	329	290	248	203	138	869	26
944	101	832	763	718	676	637	364	591	565	425	515	445	447	449	450	513	511	509	517	543	403	377	604	331	292	250	205	136	867	24
946	103	834	761	716	674	635	366	593	567	533	526	528	530	532	534	430	428	426	424	433	401	375	602	333	294	252	207	134	865	22
948	105	836	759	714	672	633	368	595	411	400	402	404	406	408	556	554	552	550	548	546	555	373	600	335	296	254	209	132	863	20
950	107	838	757	712	670	631	370	385	372	374	376	378	380	382	582	580	578	576	574	572	570	581	598	337	298	256	211	130	861	18
952	109	840	755	710	668	629	613	597	599	601	603	605	607	609	354	353	351	349	347	345	343	341	611	339	300	258	213	128	859	16
954	111	842	753	708	666	647	338	336	334	332	330	328	326	324	322	650	652	654	656	658	660	662	664	323	302	260	215	126	857	14
956	113	844	751	706	683	265	267	269	271	273	275	277	279	281	282	681	679	677	675	673	671	669	667	665	685	262	217	124	855	12
958	115	846	749	725	221	223	225	227	229	231	233	235	237	239	240	723	721	719	717	715	713	711	709	707	705	727	219	122	853	10
960	117	848	773	218	216	214	212	210	208	206	204	202	200	198	196	776	778	780	782	784	786	788	790	792	794	796	197	120	851	8
962	119	147	171	169	167	165	163	161	159	157	155	153	151	149	824	825	827	829	831	833	835	837	839	841	843	845	847	145	849	6
964	93	904	902	900	898	896	894	892	890	888	886	884	882	880	92	94	96	98	100	102	104	106	108	110	112	114	116	118	877	4
35	63	61	59	57	55	53	51	49	47	45	43	41	39	37	936	937	939	941	943	945	947	949	951	953	955	957	959	961	963	33

Below are details of **magic** and **entries** sums of **bordered** magic square of order 31. The entries sum is **minimum perfect square**:

$$\begin{array}{ll}
 S_{31 \times 31} := 15004; & T_{961} := 31 \times 15004 = 465124 = 682^2; \\
 S_{29 \times 29} := 14036; & T_{841} := 29 \times 14036 = 407044 = 638^2; \\
 S_{27 \times 27} := 13068; & T_{729} := 27 \times 13068 = 352836 = 594^2; \\
 S_{25 \times 25} := 12100; & T_{625} := 25 \times 12100 = 302500 = 550^2; \\
 S_{23 \times 23} := 11132; & T_{529} := 23 \times 11132 = 256036 = 506^2; \\
 S_{21 \times 21} := 10164; & T_{441} := 21 \times 10164 = 213444 = 462^2; \\
 S_{19 \times 19} := 9196; & T_{361} := 19 \times 9196 = 174724 = 418^2; \\
 S_{17 \times 17} := 8228; & T_{289} := 17 \times 8228 = 139876 = 374^2; \\
 S_{15 \times 15} := 7260; & T_{225} := 15 \times 7260 = 108900 = 330^2; \\
 S_{13 \times 13} := 6292; & T_{169} := 13 \times 6292 = 81796 = 286^2; \\
 S_{11 \times 11} := 5324; & T_{121} := 11 \times 5324 = 58564 = 242^2; \\
 S_{9 \times 9} := 4356; & T_{81} := 9 \times 4356 = 39204 = 198^2; \\
 S_{7 \times 7} := 3388; & T_{49} := 7 \times 3388 = 23716 = 154^2; \\
 S_{5 \times 5} := 2420; & T_{25} := 5 \times 2420 = 12100 = 110^2; \\
 S_{3 \times 3} := 1452; & T_9 := 3 \times 1452 = 4356 = 66^2; \\
 & T_1 := 484 = 22^2.
 \end{array}$$

Acknowledgement

Most of the **bordered** magic squares are calculated based on the software developed by Harry White [3, 4, ?]. Author is thankful to Harry White for keeping these software available at the link: <http://budshaw.ca/Download.html>.

25 Author's Contribution to Magic Squares and Recreation of Numbers

For author's contribution to **magic squares** and **recreation of numbers** please see the links below:

- **Inder J. Taneja**, Magic Squares, <https://inderjtaneja.com/2019/06/27/publications-magic-squares/>
- **Inder J. Taneja**, Recreation of Numbers, <https://inderjtaneja.com/2019/06/27/publications-recreation-of-numbers/>

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- [3] **H. White**, Magic Squares - <http://budshaw.ca/Download.html>
- [4] **H. White**, Block Magic Squares - <http://budshaw.ca/BlockSquares.html>
- [5] **H. White**, Magic Squares - <http://budshaw.ca/SODLS.html>

• Block-Wise Magic Squares

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• Bordered Magic Squares

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• Block-Bordered Magic Squares

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• Block-Wise and Block-Bordered Magic Squares

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• Creative Magic Squares

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